

1 **A new and almost perfectly accurate approximation of the eigenvalue effective**
2 **population size of a dioecious population: comparisons with other estimates and**
3 **detailed proofs**

4
5 Thierry de Meeûs^{1*} and Camille Noûs²

6
7 ¹ Univ Montpellier, Cirad, IRD, Intertryp, Montpellier, France. thierry.demeeus@ird.fr

8 ² Cogitamus laboratory, France, <https://www.cogitamus.fr/>. camille.nous@cogitamus.fr

9
10 * Corresponding author

11
12 Keywords: Effective population size; Dioecy; Heterozygote excess; *F*-statistics.

14 **Abstract**

15 The effective population size is an important concept in population genetics. It
16 corresponds to a measure of the speed at which genetic drift affects a given population.
17 Moreover, this is most of the time the only kind of population size that empirical population
18 genetics can give access to. Dioecious populations are expected to display excesses of
19 heterozygosity as compared to monoecious panmictic populations, as measured by
20 Wright's F_{IS} . It can be shown that these excesses are negatively correlated with the
21 population size. This is why F_{IS} can be used to estimate the eigenvalue effective
22 population size of dioecious populations. In this paper, we propose a new approximation
23 that provides a very accurate estimate of the eigenvalue effective population size of a
24 dioecious population as a function of the real population size. We then explore the
25 accuracy of different F_{IS} -based methods using the leading eigenvalue of transition matrices
26 or coalescence. It appears that the eigenvalue-based method provides more accurate
27 results in very small populations, probably due to approximations made by the
28 coalescence approach that are less valid in such situations. We also discuss the
29 applicability of this method in the field.

30

31

32

33 **Introduction**

34 A convenient way to measure the speed at which a given population loses its
35 genetic diversity by genetic drift is to compute its effective population size N_e (Vitalis &
36 Couvet, 2001b). Several formal definitions exist. They all refer to an ideal population that
37 follows all Castle-Weinberg assumptions (Castle, 1903; Weinberg, 1908) (see (De Meeûs,
38 Chan et al., 2021) for an explanation why this labelling is fairer than the more popular
39 Hardy-Weinberg), except for the size of the population that is limited to N_e . It means a self-
40 compatible diploid monoecious and panmictic population of size N_e , with no selection, no
41 migration, no mutation and discrete generations, and where alleles for the next generation
42 are binomially sampled from the $2N_e$ available ones, which causes genetic drift at a
43 specific speed, proportional to $1/(2N_e)$. Such a population is also known as following the
44 Wright-Fisher (WF) model (Crow & Kimura, 1970) , as opposed to the Castle-Weinberg
45 model, where the population is of infinite size, and thus without genetic drift. Some
46 approaches focus on the rate of inbreeding increase, the rate of heterozygosity loss, the
47 variation of allele frequencies from one generation to the other (Vitalis & Couvet, 2001b),
48 or the coalescence time (Balloux & Lehmann, 2003; Balloux, Lehmann et al., 2003;
49 Balloux, 2004; Nomura, 2008). This led authors to define the inbreeding effective
50 population size, which refers to the speed at which inbreeding evolves, the eigenvalue
51 effective population size (see appendices 1-3 to see the detailed analytical tools and
52 Appendix 4 to see why it was named as such), the variance (of allele frequencies from one
53 generation to the next) effective population size (Crow & Kimura, 1970; Vitalis & Couvet,
54 2001b; Ewens, 2004) and the coalescence (or coancestry) effective population size
55 (Balloux & Lehmann, 2003; Balloux et al., 2003; Balloux, 2004; Nomura, 2008) (see
56 below), respectively. In all cases, the effective population size is computed for a given
57 population of census size N , which deviates from an ideal population (following WF) at one
58 or several of the properties defined above. Because of these deviations, genetic drift

59 operates at a faster rate, or sometimes at a slower rate, than the same population if it
60 fulfilled the ideal conditions. The effective population size of such a non-ideal population is
61 the ideal population of size N_e that would drift at the same speed as the non-ideal one,
62 also known as the size of a population following WF and drifting at the same speed as the
63 focal population (Vitalis & Couvet, 2001b).

64 Many species have separate sexes. Several authors have investigated the impact
65 that dioecy and sex ratio have on effective population size. In this note, we review some of
66 these results and we then derive a new and apparently more accurate approximation for
67 the eigenvalue effective population size of a dioecious population. We also propose
68 another estimator of N_e from Wright's F_{IS} . We compare the relative performances of the
69 different methods. Several appendices present the proofs of all equations used in the main
70 text. These appendices are extremely detailed so that almost anybody willing to
71 understand precisely how a given result was obtained, here and in the cited literature, can
72 easily access this knowledge. Nevertheless, more skilled readers will probably not need to
73 read any of those.

74

75 **Classic results from the literature**

76 The effective population size of a dioecious population has been defined in different
77 ways. In Wright's book (Wright, 1969) (page 197), the approximate (eigenvalue) effective
78 size of a population of size N , with N_f females and N_m males is:

$$79 \quad N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} \quad (1)$$

80
81 Nevertheless, in the same book (page 197 again), a better approximation is suggested,
82 and a quick proof can be found in Felsenstein's book (pages 266-267) (Felsenstein, 2019)
83 (see also below, equation 15), for the eigenvalue effective population size N_e :

84

$$N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2}$$

85

(2)

86

More recently, Balloux (Balloux, 2004), computed the coalescence effective population

87

size as:

88

$$N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N}$$

89

(3)

90

From equations (2) and (3), and for sex-ratios (SR) that are not too female biased

91

(e.g. $N_f - N_m < \sqrt{N/2}$, for Equation 2), one can see that dioecy tends to slightly increase

92

N_e . This is obviously a consequence of the supplementary delay required for two alleles to

93

become identical by descent in the same individual, since selfing cannot occur. Another

94

consequence is that dioecious populations are expected to display heterozygote excesses

95

(Robertson, 1965). This led to formalizing the expected deviation of heterozygote

96

frequency in dioecious populations, as measured by Wright's F_{IS} (Wright, 1965), which

97

may provide a simple tool to estimate the effective population size, assuming even sex

98

ratios. Using simple algebra on observed and expected heterozygosity, Pudovkin et al.

99

(Pudovkin, Zaykin et al., 1996) proposed the following equation (see Appendix 5 for a

100

detailed proof) for the eigenvalue effective population size:

101

$$N_e = -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}}$$

102

(4)

103

They also proposed a supposedly more accurate approximation with their equation 4 (but

104

see also Appendix 5):

105

$$N_e = -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}} + \frac{1}{2(1 - F_{IS})}$$

106

(5)

107 Balloux (2004) proposed another solution, based on the coalescent effective
 108 population size and requiring quite cumbersome analytic treatments, which are detailed in
 109 Appendix 6:

$$110 \quad N_e = -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}} - \frac{F_{IS}}{(1 + F_{IS})}$$

111 (6)

112

113 **The general model of a dioecious pangamic population**

114 For now, and unless specified otherwise, we assume a dioecious diploid population
 115 of constant size and sex-ratio, with discrete generations, no mutation and no migration. At
 116 each generation, alleles that will be present in an individual of generation t were randomly
 117 drawn with replacement in the pool of gametes of their two parents (or from infinite pools
 118 of gametes), and females and males are polygamous and mate randomly. For a dioecious
 119 population with N_f females and N_m males, probabilities of identity within individuals $Q_{I(t)}$ and
 120 between individuals within the subpopulation $Q_{S(t)}$ at generation t respectively are (see for
 121 instance (Balloux, 2004), equation 14 or (Felsenstein, 2019) pages 266-267):

$$122 \quad Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)}$$

123 (7)

124 and

$$125 \quad Q_{S(t)} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_f} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_f} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right]$$

$$126 \quad + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_m} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_m} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-1)}$$

127 (8)

128 Equation 7 is straightforward: inbreeding of individuals at any generation comes from the
 129 genetic similarity between their parents. Equation 8 is less intuitive. We want to compute
 130 the probabilities of identity by descent between two alleles of two different individuals

131 taken at random at generation t , and assuming random mating of parents and a great
132 number of matings n_M (i.e. $n_M \rightarrow \infty$). This way, the probability of mating between two
133 individuals remains independent of previous copulas these may have been involved in.
134 The probability that two alleles of generation t come from two females of generation $t-1$ is
135 $\frac{1}{4}$, from two males is also $\frac{1}{4}$, and from one male and one female is $\frac{1}{2}$. If both come from
136 two females, the probability they came from the same mother is $1/N_f$ (i.e. found in full or
137 half sibs) or two different females is $1-1/N_f$. In the same diploid individual, the probability to
138 sample twice the same allele is $\frac{1}{2}$. Otherwise, two different alleles are sampled from the
139 same individual with probability $\frac{1}{2}$, but in that case they are identical by descent with
140 probability $Q_{(t-1)}$. If the two alleles came from two different females, the probability that
141 these two alleles are identical by descent is $Q_{S(t-1)}$. The same reasoning applies to the two-
142 males case. For the one-female-one-male case, the probability that the two alleles are
143 identical is also $Q_{S(t-1)}$.

144 Combining equations 7 and 8, we get:

$$145 \quad Q_{S(t)} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_f} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-2)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_f} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right]$$

$$146 \quad + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_m} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-2)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_m} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-1)}$$

147 \Leftrightarrow

$$148 \quad Q_{S(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \frac{1}{4} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_f} + 1 - \frac{1}{N_m} + 2 \right) + Q_{S(t-2)} \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{2N_f} + \frac{1}{2N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{1}{2N_f} + \frac{1}{2N_m} \right)$$

149 \Leftrightarrow

$$150 \quad Q_{S(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N_m - N_f}{N_f N_m} \right) + Q_{S(t-2)} \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N_f + N_m}{N_f N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N_f + N_m}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

151 \Leftrightarrow

$$152 \quad Q_{S(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) + Q_{S(t-2)} \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

153 Using the genetic diversity of the subpopulation $H_s = 1 - Q_s$ yields simpler expressions:

$$154 \quad 1 - H_{S(t)} = (1 - H_{S(t-1)}) \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) + (1 - H_{S(t-2)}) \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

$$155 \quad H_{S(t)} = 1 - (1 - H_{S(t-1)}) \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) - (1 - H_{S(t-2)}) \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right) - \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

156 \Leftrightarrow

$$157 \quad H_{S(t)} = 1 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{4} H_{S(t-1)} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) - \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{8} H_{S(t-2)} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

$$158 \quad - \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

159 \Leftrightarrow

$$160 \quad H_{S(t)} = H_{S(t-1)} \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{N_f N_m} \right) + H_{S(t-2)} \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{N_f N_m} \right) + 1 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N + N}{N_f N_m} \right)$$

161 \Leftrightarrow

$$162 \quad H_{S(t)} = H_{S(t-1)} \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{4N_f N_m} + H_{S(t-2)} \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}$$

$$163 \quad (9)$$

164 Let λ be:

$$165 \quad \lambda = \frac{H_{S(t)}}{H_{S(t-1)}}$$

$$166 \quad (10)$$

167 Assuming λ to be constant from one generation to the next, and dividing all terms by $H_{S(t-1)}$,

168 Equation 10 writes:

$$169 \quad \lambda = \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{4N_f N_m} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}$$

170 \Leftrightarrow

$$171 \quad \lambda^2 - \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{4N_f N_m} \lambda = \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}$$

172 \Leftrightarrow

173
$$\lambda^2 - 2 \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \lambda + \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2 = \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2$$

174 \Leftrightarrow

175
$$\left(\lambda - \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2 = \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2$$

176 \Leftrightarrow

177
$$\lambda = \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \pm \sqrt{\frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2}$$

178 As λ is positive, the single positive (leading) root of this equation is:

179
$$\lambda = \frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} + \sqrt{\frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{4N_f N_m - N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2}$$

180 \Leftrightarrow

181
$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \sqrt{\frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} \right)^2}$$

182 \Leftrightarrow

183
$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{N}{2N_f N_m} + \left(1 - \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2}$$

184 \Leftrightarrow

185
$$\lambda = \frac{1 - \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} + \sqrt{\frac{N}{2N_f N_m} + 1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2} - 2 \frac{N}{4N_f N_m}}{2}$$

186 \Leftrightarrow

187
$$\lambda = \frac{1 - \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2}}{2}$$

188 (11)

189 Note that the same results can be obtained with the leading eigenvalue of the transition
 190 matrix describing the evolution of genetic identities (Appendix 7).

191 For a monoecious panmictic population:

192
$$H_{S(t)} = H_{S(t-1)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}\right)$$

193 and in that case:

194
$$\lambda = 1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}$$

195 (12)

196 We now need to combine Equations 11 and 12 to get:

197
$$1 - \frac{1}{2N_e} = \frac{1 - \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}}{2}$$

198 ⇔

199
$$\frac{1}{2N_e} = 1 - \frac{1 - \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}}{2}$$

200 ⇔

201
$$\frac{1}{2N_e} = \frac{2 - 1 + \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}}{2}$$

202 ⇔

203
$$\frac{1}{N_e} = 1 + \frac{N}{4N_f N_m} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}$$

204 ⇔

205
$$N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{4N_f N_m + N - 4N_f N_m \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}}$$

206 ⇔

$$N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{4N_f N_m \left[1 - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2} \right] + N}$$

208 (13)

209

210 A new approximation

211 According to Taylor-MacLaurin's expansion series, $\sqrt{1+X} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2}X - \frac{1}{8}X^2$ (see

212 Appendix 8 for a detailed proof). We can thus approximate the square root in equation 13

213 with:

$$214 \quad \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^4 + \dots$$

215 The quantity $4N_f N_m$ is the lowest for the most uneven sex-ratios, like $N_m=1$ and $N_f=N-1$. In

216 that case:

$$217 \quad -\frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^4 + \dots = -\frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{N}{4(N-1)} \right)^4 + \dots = -\frac{1}{32} \left(\frac{N}{N-1} \right)^4 + \dots \ll 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2$$

218 We can then consider that:

$$219 \quad \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2$$

220 Eq 13 can thus write:

$$221 \quad N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{4N_f N_m \left[1 - 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2 \right] + N}$$

222 \Leftrightarrow

$$223 \quad N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{-2N_f N_m \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m} \right)^2 + N}$$

224 \Leftrightarrow

225
$$N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{N - \frac{N^2}{8N_f N_m}}$$

226 \Leftrightarrow

227
$$N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}}$$

228 (14)

229 Using Taylor-MacLaurin again we can see that: $1/(1-X)=1+X+X^2+X^3+\dots$ (Appendix 8).

230 We can thus rewrite the second term of the denominator of equation 14:

231
$$\frac{1}{1 - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}} \approx 1 + \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^3 + \dots$$

232 Using this in equation 14 yields:

233
$$N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} \times \frac{1}{1 - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m}} = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} \left(1 + \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^3 + \dots\right)$$

234 \Leftrightarrow

235
$$N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{N}{8N_f N_m}\right)^3 + \dots$$

236 For the same reasons as those given above, in this equation, terms that are squared,
237 cubed etc... can be neglected, and we then get:

238
$$N_e \approx \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{N}{4N_f N_m}$$

239 (15)

240 Note that if we neglect $N/(16N_f N_m)$, we obtain equation 2.

241 For an even sex ratio, we get:

242
$$N_e \approx N + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4N}$$

243 (16)

244 Equations 15 and 16 are a little different from Balloux's equations 18 and 10 (Balloux,
245 2004), respectively:

$$246 \quad \begin{cases} N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N} \\ N_e \approx N + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

247 The reasons for this discrepancy between these two sets of equations are unclear due to
248 the lack of details in Balloux' paper. For his equation 10, Balloux simply cites Wright's book
249 (Wright, 1969) without mentioning the page or the equation number. A glance at Wright's
250 book only provided a stronger approximation (page 212, equation 8.4): $N_e=N+1/2$, without
251 giving much details (but see Felsenstein's book page 266-267 (Felsenstein, 2019)).
252 Appendix 6 provides a detailed proof for Balloux's equation 10 in the (simpler) case of
253 even sex-ratios.

254 In Figure 1, it can be seen that the first approximation found in Wright's book
255 (Equation 1), as in all population genetics textbooks, strongly underestimates N_e , except
256 for very big populations (as expected), as compared to other approximations. Wright's
257 second equation and Balloux's one seem to display an equivalently small bias, though in
258 varying directions for Balloux's equation, depending on the sex-ratio. This can be seen
259 with a study of the sign of $\Delta N_{e_B} = N_{e_Eq3} - N_{e_Eq13}$ (see appendix 9), where we notice that
260 with the unique valid root of ΔN_e (SR_2), Balloux's equation will provide an over-estimate
261 when $SR > SR_2$, an under-estimate when $SR < SR_2$ and will be accurate when $SR = SR_2 = 3 -$
262 $2\sqrt{2} \approx 0.1716$ (e.g. $SR \approx 1/6$; $SR \approx 4/23$). From there, it is easily deduced that, in Figure 1,
263 positive values of ΔN_{e_B} correspond to $SR > SR_2$, negative ones to $SR < SR_2$, and close or
264 very close to accuracy around this threshold (for instance $35/204$ is very close to SR_2).
265 This bias is very small when $N_e > 10$ (Figure 1). Finally, the new simplified estimate
266 proposed in Equation 15 perfectly fits to Equation 13, except for very small $N_e < 4$ where a
267 very small overestimate can be noticed (Figure 1).

268

269

270

271

272

273

274

275

276

Figure 1: Comparisons of the performances of different approximations of effective population size (N_{e_a}) in dioecious populations with uneven (left) and even (right) sex-ratios, as compared to equation 13 (Eq 13) (N_e). Performance was measured as $\Delta_e=(N_{e_a}-N_e)/N_e$, with Wright's equations 1 and 2 (Eq1 and Eq2 respectively), Balloux (Eq3), and the new simplified estimate of the present paper (Eq15).

276

Estimating the effective population size from Wright's F_{IS}

277

278

279

280

As seen above with equations 4, 5 and 6, heterozygote excesses expected in pangamic dioecious populations as computed by Wright's F_{IS} , can give access to an estimate of N_e from genotypic data. In the following, we propose other F_{IS} based estimates.

281

282

283

284

Let H_{exp} and H_{obs} be the expected (under Castle-Weinberg expectations) and the observed proportion of heterozygotes in the population, respectively. We can express these proportions as the probabilities of drawing at random two different alleles in the population $H_{S(t)}$ and in an individual $H_{I(t)}$ respectively at any generation t : $H_{exp}=H_{S(t)}$ and

285 $H_{obs}=H_{l(t)}$. Finally, from equation 7, we can see that $H_{l(t)}= H_{S(t-1)}$. If we take Nei's parametric
 286 definition of F_{IS} (Nei & Chesser, 1983):

287
$$F_{IS} = \frac{H_{exp} - H_{obs}}{H_{exp}}$$

288 \Leftrightarrow

289
$$F_{IS} = 1 - \frac{H_{obs}}{H_{exp}}$$

290 \Leftrightarrow

291
$$F_{IS} = 1 - \frac{H_{S(t-1)}}{H_{S(t)}}$$

292 (17)

293 We can combine equations 10 and 17 to obtain:

294
$$F_{IS} = 1 - \frac{1}{\lambda}$$

295 (18)

296 Now, combining equation 18 with equation 12 yields:

297
$$F_{IS} = 1 - \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}}$$

298 \Leftrightarrow

299
$$F_{IS} = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2N_e} - 1}{1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}}$$

300 \Leftrightarrow

301
$$F_{IS} = \frac{-\frac{1}{2N_e}}{1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}}$$

302 \Leftrightarrow

303
$$F_{IS} = -\frac{1}{2N_e - 1}$$

304 ⇔

$$305 \quad 2N_e F_{IS} - F_{IS} = -1$$

306 ⇔

$$307 \quad N_e = \frac{F_{IS} - 1}{2F_{IS}}$$

308 ⇔

$$309 \quad N_e = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2F_{IS}}$$

310 (19)

311 This result is the same as Equation 4 plus one half of an individual.

312 We can also express N as a function of F_{IS} in a dioecious population with an even
313 sex-ratio (Appendix 10):

$$314 \quad N = -\frac{1 + F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}}$$

315 (20)

316 Here, N can be called the effective number of breeders, which must not be confused with
317 the effective population size. Notice that equation 20 differs from equation 4 by the
318 subtraction of half an individual.

319 If we use Equation 20 in Equation 16 and rearrange the formula we get (Appendix 9):

$$320 \quad N_e \approx -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}} - \frac{F_{IS}}{2(1 + F_{IS})}$$

321 (21)

322 We can here note that, if we use equation 20 in equation 2 ((Wright, 1969), page 197),
323 with an even sex-ratio, we obtain equation 4 (first F_{IS} based estimate of Pudovkin et al
324 (Pudovkin et al., 1996)).

325 We have estimated F_{IS} based N_e under various population sizes and sex-ratios,
326 using the expected F_{IS} computed in Appendix 11:

327

$$F_{IS} \approx -\frac{N_m + N_f}{N_m + N_f + 8N_m N_f}$$

328

(22)

329

In the Figure 2, it can be seen that, as compared to expected values (Equation 13)

330

Equations 5 (Pudovkin et al second equation) and 19 (simple equation of the present

331

paper) tend to over-estimate N_e as compared to other estimates, unless population size

332

becomes big enough. Equations 4 (Pudovkin et al first equation) and 6 (Balloux) present

333

an equivalent bias but in the opposite direction (under-estimate and over-estimate,

334

respectively). This bias is only visible for small N_e 's (i.e. $N_e < 10$). Interestingly, the average

335

of these two is exactly equation 21 of the present study, which fits perfectly with the

336

expected one, with an extremely small over-estimate for the smallest $N_e < 3$.

337

338

339 Figure 2: Comparisons of the performances of different F_{IS} based (Equation 22) estimates
 340 of effective population size (N_{e_a}) in dioecious populations, as compared to equation 13
 341 (Eq 13) (N_e), measured as $\Delta_e = (N_{e_a} - N_e) / N_e$, with Pudovkin et al. equations 1 and 2 (Eq 4
 342 and Eq 5 respectively), Balloux (Eq 6), and the new simplified estimates of the present
 343 paper: the most simple (Eq 19), and the final one (Eq 21).

344

345

346 Discussion

347 Genetic drift can be influenced by several factors other than dioecy, population size
 348 and sex-ratio: reproductive variance, non-overlapping generations, changes in population
 349 size and/or sex ratio, subdivision and selection. Such complications may lead to very
 350 cumbersome algebra if one wanted to present a more general expression for the effective
 351 population size.

352 The main goals of the present study were, in decreasing order of importance. 1) to
 353 present an improved approximation of the classic case where only dioecy and/or uneven
 354 sex-ratio have an effect and compare it to previous approximations; 2) to present detailed
 355 derivations of both the old and new results that would be accessible to most readers; and

356 3) to provide an improved F_{IS} estimate deriving from this new approximation, to be used in
357 empirical population genetics studies instead of the two most often used methods:
358 Pudovkin et al. (Pudovkin et al., 1996) and Balloux (Balloux, 2004) (11 and 8 citations per
359 year respectively according to Google scholar's based research in the computer program
360 Publish and Perish 8.8.4275.8412 (Harzing, 2007)).

361 We do not expect any natural population to closely follow the model we explored in
362 the present work. Nevertheless, excluding reproductive system variation and selection,
363 any combination of the factors mentioned above will tend to reduce N_e and F_{IS} accordingly,
364 and most probably their variance, with not much harm to the average expectations. Partial
365 selfing (e.g. deriving from some kinds of automictic parthenogenesis of females (De
366 Meeûs, Prugnolle et al., 2007)), or partial sib-mating, should be easily detected, produce
367 generalized heterozygote deficits and thus exclude our method. Clonal propagation (e.g.
368 through a special kind of endomitotic automixis of females (De Meeûs et al., 2007)) should
369 also be easy to detect (De Meeûs, Lehmann et al., 2006) and again the F_{IS} based method
370 would be dismissed. Selection is locus specific and should only affect one or two of the loci
371 used, which consequently should be easy to detect and exclude. Subdivision can have two
372 effects: if there is a Wahlund effect, this should be easy to detect (Manangwa, De Meeûs
373 et al., 2019); and if not, highly subdivided populations should exhibit effective sub-
374 population sizes that are very close to the one that these would exhibit if totally isolated
375 (because rare immigrants are not expected to display much influence), and if not,
376 subsamples should all converge toward the total effective population size, which should be
377 easily detected too (Ravel, Mahamat et al., 2023) (see also (Waples & Do, 2010; Waples
378 & England, 2011)). Additionally, in most situation, empiricists have no idea of the effective
379 sex-ratio, of the scenarios regarding how generations overlap, or how population size
380 fluctuates across generations. Consequently, complication of estimates will neither allow
381 an easy understanding of the mathematical developments, which was an important goal of

382 the present work, nor take into account with certainty the real scenarios that occurred in
383 the population under investigation. This is why, even if the new estimate will hardly give
384 significantly different values as compared to the previous ones, we think it is still better
385 using the theoretical one that is closer to the exact expected value (equation 21) and
386 interpretable on more sound biological means (see below).

387 The new approximation proposed in Equation 15 is equivalent to what is expected
388 in large dioecious populations (Equation 1), plus half an individual, plus half of a coalesced
389 individual in a large dioecious population. As far as we know, such added quantities were
390 never discussed before (but see Felsenstein 2019, page 266). We can here try to provide
391 some biological interpretation of such quantities. One half of heterozygosity is lost when an
392 individual reproduces by selfing. In a panmictic population (i.e. monoecious) of size N , a
393 proportion $1/N$ of gametes are produced by selfing (Rousset, 1996), in which case half the
394 genes coalesce in the progeny ($P_{CM}=1/2N$). This can happen in the N individuals. Hence
395 $(1/N) \times (1/2) \times N = 1/2$ individuals are produced with coalesced genes per generation through
396 selfing in a WF population. This means that one half of such coalescent event does not
397 happen when random selfing is forbidden, as it is necessarily the case in dioecious
398 populations. Additionally, in very big dioecious populations, $N_e \approx 4N_f N_m / N$ (Equation 1). For
399 any diploid population, the instantaneous probability of coalescence is $P_C = 1/(2N_e)$ (see
400 (Laporte & Charlesworth, 2002), Equation 7; or (Nomura, 2008) Equation 3).

401 Consequently, for a very big dioecious population, this probability becomes (Equation 1)
402 $P_{CBD} = (1/2) \times N / (4N_f N_m)$. The number of individuals concerned are those that inherited twice
403 the same allele from their grand-parents, which is $(1/N_f) \times (1/4) \times N_f$ for females and
404 $(1/N_m) \times (1/4) \times N_m$ for males, hence $1/2$ individuals. This yields $P_{CBD} \times (1/2)$ individuals. In
405 small dioecious populations, such coalescent events hardly happen, because as long as
406 polymorphism is kept, male and female parents that mate randomly can only rarely have
407 sampled twice the same alleles from the same grand-parent. These two differences with 1)

408 panmictic populations, and 2) big dioecious populations, may explain Equation 15. In other
409 words, if we call N_{e_BD} the effective population size of a very big dioecious population,
410 N_{NCNS} the number of individuals that cannot be coalescent due to the absence of selfing
411 and N_{NCSD} the number of individuals that cannot be coalescent in a dioecious population
412 due to the limited number of possible mates, then, in small dioecious populations, the
413 effective population size is $N_{e_SD} = N_{e_BD} + N_{NCNS} + N_{NCSD}$.

414 Interestingly, the highly sophisticated, and fairly complicated to compute, Balloux's
415 equation (Balloux, 2004), Equation 3 in the present paper, did not perform better than
416 Wright's second equation (Equation 2), and worse than our Equation 15. As shown in
417 Appendix 6, the coalescence effective population size was obtained after neglecting
418 different terms at several successive steps of the analytical process. To be as accurate as
419 Equation 21, Equation 2 indeed requires $N_e > 10$ and/or a sufficient number of generations
420 (e.g. 10). As seen from the Figure 1, this seems to indeed apply as long as $N_e > 12$. No
421 explanations were provided for the abstract notion of the coalescence effective population
422 size and the way used to weight approximated coalescent times computed at different
423 hierarchical levels (e.g. individuals, subpopulations, etc...). What we were interested in, in
424 this paper, was to compute the local effective population size, i.e. the one that affects the
425 speed of polymorphism loss within subpopulations. In that case, the eigenvalue effective
426 population size may be the most accurate.

427 Regarding F_{IS} -based estimates, the fact that Pudovkin et al 2nd equation ((Pudovkin
428 et al., 1996), equation 5) did not perform well, probably comes from the confusion between
429 effective population size and the number of individuals (or of breeders), at different steps
430 of the analytical procedure. Equation 19 provided similar results as equation 5, though with
431 a slightly stronger bias and is thus too biased also. Pudovkin et al's second equation
432 (equation 5 of the present manuscript), is quite popular in empirical population genetics
433 studies, and is the one implemented in NeEstimator (Do, Waples et al., 2014). It presented

434 underestimates, even when $N_e > 20$. Balloux's equation (equation 6), also popular, suffered
435 from an overestimation of N_e , in a symmetric position as compared to underestimations of
436 Equation 4 (Pudovkin et al. first equation). For both, the biases are small, particularly so
437 when $N_e > 4$. Interestingly, following the steps described in Balloux's paper (Balloux, 2004),
438 but replacing the coalescence approach by the leading eigenvalue approach, provided the
439 most accurate F_{IS} -based estimate of the effective population size in dioecious populations
440 (Equation 21). It appeared to exactly correspond to the average between Equations 4
441 (Pudovkin et al first equation) and 6 (Balloux).

442 It is worth recalling that the F_{IS} -based estimates given in Equation 21 assumes an
443 even sex ratio. Nevertheless, strongly biased sex-ratios will affect F_{IS} accordingly and
444 should not have strong consequences on the estimate of effective population sizes, as
445 suggested by the Figure 2.

446 We may also bear in mind that although random mating was assumed, we did not
447 specify any reproductive strategy (mono or polygamy). Indeed, Equation 8 assumes
448 polygamy, but monogamy is known to lead to the same result as polygamy, as
449 demonstrated pages 267-268 in Felsenstein's book (Felsenstein, 2019), and in Appendix
450 12. The only difference is that, in monogamous populations, the sex-ratio of individuals
451 that reproduce is necessarily even. Consequently, monogamy can prevent a possible high
452 variance in male mating success, which would reduce N_e . But monogamy cannot produce
453 an increase of N_e as compared to pangamic polygamy. In that sense, and everything else
454 being equal, gibbons (which are monogamous) should preserve better their genetic
455 diversity than gorillas, but not better than bonobos (assuming bonobos are pangamous).

456 It is worth mentioning that these computations were based on accurate (exact)
457 measures of F_{IS} . Unbiased estimators of F -statistics (Weir & Cockerham, 1984) suffer from
458 large variances (Robertson & Hill, 1984). It is thus likely that deviation from the real value
459 will have a large impact on F_{IS} -based estimates of N_e , especially for small expected

460 ("real") values. It can be seen that $N_{e_Eq4} < N_{e_Eq21} < N_{e_Eq6} < N_{e_Eq5} < N_{e_Eq19}$. From there, it can
461 be expected that with small underestimations of F_{IS} , N_{e_Eq6} will be closer to the real value;
462 then N_{e_Eq5} for bigger underestimations, and finally N_{e_Eq19} for the strongest
463 underestimations. On the contrary, overestimations of F_{IS} will necessarily lead N_{e_Eq4} to
464 stay closer to the real N_e . However, the differences are expected to be quite small,
465 particularly so as compared to Pudovkin 1 (Equation 4) and Balloux (Equation 6),
466 especially for the highest values (e.g. $N_e > 6$): Nevertheless, not knowing what the real F_{IS}
467 should be, it is probably wiser using the less biased estimate, i.e. N_{e_Eq21} .

468 It is also worth mentioning that F_{IS} should be estimated from adults, as the genetic
469 structure in immature individuals may considerably differ from the one they would display
470 in the pool of adults that survived.

471 The fact that our equation 21 outperformed other equations for $N_e < 4-6$ may suggest
472 strong limitations in the practical applicability of this performance since such systems may
473 be expected to quickly undergo extinction. In addition to the fact that it is generally
474 preferable to work with the most accurate equation, these results are likely to be especially
475 pertinent for certain types of biological systems that are able to persist for extended
476 periods despite having very small effective population sizes. For instance, the populations
477 of the parasitoid wasp *Nasonia vitripennis*, depending on the distribution of its host
478 (parasitic flies), often display systematic mating of females with their brothers (Werren,
479 1980). For the mite *Varroa destructor*, a female enters a brood cell, which she caps, where
480 she feeds on the bee larva and then gives birth to a haploid male, which later mates with
481 its diploid sisters, laid by the mother from fertilized eggs from a previous mating that
482 occurred before the colonization of the brood cell, or after mating with her son (which may
483 happen for 30% of females) (Beaurepaire, Krieger et al., 2017; Häußermann, Giacobino et
484 al., 2020). In both cases, males are produced by arrhenotokous parthenogenesis
485 (unfertilized haploid eggs), meaning that many populations of these organisms probably

486 display very small N_e , and even smaller than 1 in some instances. We did not undertake
487 an extensive review of similar cases, as it is not in the scope of the present paper, but
488 such kind of situations may not be rare in dioecious parasitic organisms like parasitoid
489 hymenoptera, mites or nematodes.

490 According to recent papers based on simulations (i.e. perfect data), F_{IS} -based
491 single sample (or subsample) estimates of N_e are not the most accurate (Wang, 2009; Do
492 et al., 2014; Wang, 2016). According to Do et al (2014), the linkage disequilibrium (LD)
493 based estimate (Waples, 2006), appeared to perform better than the co-ancestry method
494 (CoA) (Nomura, 2008) and the F_{IS} -based method (Equation 5) (Pudovkin et al., 1996).
495 According to more recent simulation studies (Wang, 2016), the sibship frequency based
496 estimate (SF) (Wang, 2009) seemed to provide more accurate results than the previous
497 ones. No comparison was ever made with an alternative method based on one and two
498 locus identity measures (1&2LI) (Vitalis & Couvet, 2001c, b), implemented by the software
499 Estim 1.2.2 (Vitalis, 2002), updated from Estim 1 (Vitalis & Couvet, 2001a). Based on
500 simulations, the 1&2LI method provided accurate (though slightly underestimated) results,
501 especially when more than four loci were used (Vitalis & Couvet, 2001b). Again, no
502 simulation study exhaustively compared all available one-sample estimates. This would
503 require replicated simulations of different scenarios of population structure (Island or
504 stepping stone models with varying subpopulation number, sub-population sizes and
505 immigration rates), different kinds of loci (microsatellite like or SNP like loci) with varying
506 number of loci, number of alleles and mutation rates, and with or without amplification
507 problems (null alleles, stuttering, short allele dominance or allelic dropouts), and varying
508 sampling strategies. A comparison with temporal methods (Nei & Tajima, 1981; Pollak,
509 1983; Wang & Whitlock, 2003; Jorde & Ryman, 2007) might also prove interesting, though
510 the number of generations between two samples of the same site will add another relevant

511 parameter to explore (Waples & Do, 2010). This will obviously require much more work to
512 undertake, which is beyond the scope of the present paper.

513 We nevertheless undertook a quick simulation study with Easypop (Balloux, 2001).
514 We simulated single isolated and randomly mating dioecious populations, with varying
515 sex-ratio, at 100 independent loci with a KAM model of mutation with $K=100$ possible
516 allelic states and a mutation rate of $u=0.00001$, and 100 generations. All simulations
517 started with maximum diversity. We then computed effective population sizes. We
518 computed F_{IS} with Fstat (Goudet, 1995). For these simulations, most of the averaged F_{IS}
519 across loci were positive and therefore could not be used to estimate N_e . We then
520 preferred computing the average across loci displaying a negative F_{IS} . For NeEstimator
521 analyses (LD and Coancestries), we assumed polygamy and kept estimates excluding
522 alleles less frequent than 5% (LD method). For Estim (1&2LI), we assumed panmixia. For
523 Colony (SF), we generated data using Create (Coombs, Letcher et al., 2008) and
524 assumed polygamy and some inbreeding, as this may occur at unknown level in real data.
525 Figure 3 illustrates what kind of variations could be observed from one parameter set to
526 the other and from one method to the other. It suggests that some kind of average across
527 methods may allow grasping the range of actual effective population sizes of sub-
528 populations from genotyped sub-samples.

529

530

531

532

533

534

535

536

537

538

539

540

541

542

543

544

545

Figure 3: Effective population size estimates (N_e) with five different methods as compared to the expected value (Equation 22), for different simulated populations with varying numbers of females (N_f) and males (N_m).

Regarding real data, quoting Nomura, "combined estimate of several independent estimates is expected to improve the precision of separate estimates" (Nomura, 2008). For each method, one could compute the average N_e across subsamples of the same population, ignoring undefined values (negative or infinite), note the maximum and minimum values obtained and keep the number of usable values as a weight. Finally, the grand average (across methods) and average minimum and maximum, all weighted by the number of usable values obtained in each method, could be computed. For more clarity, a template of this method can be found in the file "TemplateRhipicephalusFstatResNeFiveMethods.xlsx", coming from the analysis of cattle tick populations from New-Caledonia (De Meeûs, Koffi et al., 2010). With all data, average $N_e \approx 120$ in $\text{minimax} \approx [80, 200]$. When excluding the two most extreme values $N_e \approx 50$ in

546 minimax \approx [10, 110]. Using the harmonic mean, as suggested by Nomura (Nomura, 2008),
547 $N_e \approx 20$ in minimax=[10, 30]. Simulation studies could be used to identify an estimator that
548 more accurately approximates the eigenvalue effective population size of genotyped
549 populations.

550 Temporal data are rarely available (but see (Palstra & Ruzzante, 2008)), but when
551 these are, they give access to different estimates, which may be usefully included in the
552 computations of averages and magnitude of variations.

553 Undefined N_e may correspond to very big values. Thus, ignoring these may lead to
554 underestimates. They may also correspond to the variance of estimate of the parameter
555 used, like F_{IS} , as mentioned above. This possible flaw may be attenuated by the use of
556 repeated subsamples and independent loci. Waples and Do proposed to include negative
557 N_e as such in the computation of an harmonic mean, with weights proportional to
558 reciprocals of variances (Waples & Do, 2010). Nevertheless, on the tick data set, this
559 strategy ended with globally negative (and then unsound) values for these populations (not
560 shown), which are expected to display important population sizes (i.e. $120 \leq N_e \leq 1200$
561 (Koffi, De Meeûs et al., 2006)). As already discussed, this will require a more thorough
562 exploration through simulations of various kinds of populations.

563 To conclude, even if the differences with some other equations are not very big, the
564 new approximation proposed here appeared almost perfect and biologically relatively
565 sound, and, wherever it is used for, we suggest to use it instead of the previous and more
566 biased estimates found in the literature.

567

568 **Acknowledgements**

569 Thierry de Meeûs would like to thank François Rousset, François Ziegler and
570 members of the Maxima-discuss list for recurrently answering to my queries and for giving
571 me tips that really unblocked the advances of the present work. Special thanks to Joseph

572 Felsenstein who gave the idea of using Taylor-MacLaurin series, which triggered the
573 transformation of a small paragraph of a book into a full article. We also are grateful to
574 Robin Waples, Jay Taylor and two anonymous referees, whose comments considerably
575 helped improving this manuscript, as Myriam Heuertz for her significant editorial inputs.
576 This work was entirely financed by the Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD)
577 (recurring subsidies of UMR Intertryp).

578

579 **Authors' contributions**

580 All authors read, amended and/or approved the final manuscript.

581 Conceptualization: Thierry de Meeûs, Camille Noûs.

582 Simulations and analyses: Thierry de Meeûs.

583 Design of figures: Thierry de Meeûs.

584 Writing of the original draft: Thierry de Meeûs.

585 Supervision: Thierry de Meeûs.

586

587 **Data availability**

588 Simulations used for the graphic of Figure 3 are available in the file "Simulations-
589 1st-pop.zip" in Zenodo. Maxima scripts are provided in the section Scripts at the end of the
590 manuscript. The template "TemplateRhipicephalusFstatResNeFiveMethods.xlsx", with the
591 corresponding dataset "BoophilusAdultsDataCattle.txt", and the file VarDif.pdf
592 (computation of the variance of a difference) are also available in Zenodo.

593

594 **Conflict of interest disclosure**

595 The authors declare that they have no financial conflict of interest with the
596 content of this article. Thierry de Meeûs is one of the PCI Infections administrators.

597

598 **References**

- 599 Balloux, F. (2001) EASYPOP (version 1.7): A computer program for population genetics
600 simulations. *Journal of Heredity*, **92**, 301-302. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jhered/92.3.301>
- 601 Balloux, F. (2004) Heterozygote excess in small populations and the heterozygote-excess
602 effective population size. *Evolution*, **58**, 1891-1900. <https://doi.org/10.1554/03-692>
- 603 Balloux, F., Lehmann, L. (2003) Random mating with a finite number of matings. *Genetics*,
604 **165**, 2313-2315. <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/165.4.2313>
- 605 Balloux, F., Lehmann, L., De Meeûs, T. (2003) The population genetics of clonal and
606 partially clonal diploids. *Genetics*, **164**, 1635-1644.
607 <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/164.4.1635>
- 608 Beaurepaire, A.L., Krieger, K.J., Moritz, R.F.A. (2017) Seasonal cycle of inbreeding and
609 recombination of the parasitic mite *Varroa destructor* in honeybee colonies and its
610 implications for the selection of acaricide resistance. *Infection Genetics and Evolution*, **50**,
611 49-54. 10.1016/j.meegid.2017.02.011
- 612 Castle, W.E. (1903) The laws of heredity of Galton and Mendel, and some laws governing
613 race improvement by selection. *Proceedings of the American Academy of Arts and*
614 *Sciences*, **39**, 223-242. <https://doi.org/10.2307/20021870>
- 615 Coombs, J.A., Letcher, B.H., Nislow, K.H. (2008) CREATE: a software to create input files
616 from diploid genotypic data for 52 genetic software programs. *Molecular Ecology*
617 *Resources*, **8**, 578–580. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1471-8286.2007.02036.x>
- 618 Crow, J.F., Kimura, M. (1970) *An Introduction to Population Genetics Theory*. The
619 Blackburn Press, Caldwell, New-Jersey.
- 620 De Meeûs, T., Chan, C.T., Ludwig, J.M., Tsao, J.I., Patel, J., Bhagatwala, J., Beati, L.
621 (2021) Deceptive combined effects of short allele dominance and stuttering: an example
622 with *Ixodes scapularis*, the main vector of Lyme disease in the U.S.A. *Peer Community*
623 *Journal*, **1**, e40. <https://doi.org/10.24072/pcjournal.34>

624 De Meeûs, T., Koffi, B.B., Barré, N., de Garine-Wichatitsky, M., Chevillon, C. (2010) Swift
625 sympatric adaptation of a species of cattle tick to a new deer host in New-Caledonia.
626 *Infection Genetics and Evolution*, **10**, 976-983.
627 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2010.06.005>

628 De Meeûs, T., Lehmann, L., Balloux, F. (2006) Molecular epidemiology of clonal diploids:
629 A quick overview and a short DIY (do it yourself) notice. *Infection Genetics and Evolution*,
630 **6**, 163-170. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meegid.2005.02.004>

631 De Meeûs, T., Prugnolle, F., Agnew, P. (2007) Asexual reproduction: Genetics and
632 evolutionary aspects. *Cellular and Molecular Life Sciences*, **64**, 1355-1372.
633 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00018-007-6515-2>

634 Do, C., Waples, R.S., Peel, D., Macbeth, G.M., Tillett, B.J., Ovenden, J.R. (2014)
635 NeEstimator v2: re-implementation of software for the estimation of contemporary effective
636 population size (N_e) from genetic data. *Molecular Ecology Resources*, **14**, 209-214.
637 10.1111/1755-0998.12157

638 Ewens, W.J. (2004) *Mathematical Population Genetics: I. Theoretical Introduction*, 2nd
639 Edition. Springer, New York.

640 Felsenstein, J. (2019) *Theoretical Evolutionary Genetics*. Department of Genome
641 Sciences and Department of Biology, University of Washington, Seattle, Washington.

642 Goudet, J. (1995) FSTAT (Version 1.2): A computer program to calculate F-statistics.
643 *Journal of Heredity*, **86**, 485-486. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.jhered.a111627>

644 Harzing, A.W. (2007) Publish or Perish, available from
645 <https://harzing.com/resources/publish-or-perish>.

646 Häußermann, C.K., Giacobino, A., Munz, R., Ziegelmann, B., Palacio, M.A., Rosenkranz,
647 P. (2020) Reproductive parameters of female *Varroa destructor* and the impact of mating
648 in worker brood of *Apis mellifera*. *Apidologie*, **51**, 342-355.
649 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s13592-019-00713-9>

650 Horn, R.A., Johnson, C.R. (2013) *Matrix Analysis, Second Edition*. Cambridge University
651 Press, Cambridge, UK.

652 Jorde, P.E., Ryman, N. (2007) Unbiased estimator for genetic drift and effective population
653 size. *Genetics*, **177**, 927-935.

654 Koffi, B.B., De Meeûs, T., Barré, N., Durand, P., Arnathau, C., Chevillon, C. (2006)
655 Founder effects, inbreeding and effective sizes in the Southern cattle tick: the effect of
656 transmission dynamics and implications for pest management. *Molecular Ecology*, **15**,
657 4603-4611.

658 Laporte, V., Charlesworth, B. (2002) Effective population size and population subdivision
659 in demographically structured populations. *Genetics*, **162**, 501-519.

660 Manangwa, O., De Meeûs, T., Grébaut, P., Segard, A., Byamungu, M., Ravel, S. (2019)
661 Detecting Wahlund effects together with amplification problems : cryptic species, null
662 alleles and short allele dominance in *Glossina pallidipes* populations from Tanzania.
663 *Molecular Ecology Resources*, **19**, 757-772. 10.1111/1755-0998.12989

664 Nei, M., Chesser, R.K. (1983) Estimation of fixation indices and gene diversities. *Annals of*
665 *Human Genetics*, **47**, 253-259. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-1809.1983.tb00993.x>

666 Nei, M., Tajima, F. (1981) Genetic drift and estimation of effective population size.
667 *Genetics*, **98**, 625-640.

668 Nomura, T. (2008) Estimation of effective number of breeders from molecular coancestry
669 of single cohort sample. *Evolutionary Applications*, **1**, 462-474.

670 Palstra, F.P., Ruzzante, D.E. (2008) Genetic estimates of contemporary effective
671 population size: what can they tell us about the importance of genetic stochasticity for wild
672 population persistence? *Molecular Ecology*, **17**, 3428-3447. 10.1111/j.1365-
673 294X.2008.03842.x

674 Pollak, E. (1983) A new method for estimating the effective population size from allele
675 frequency changes. *Genetics*, **104**, 531-548.

676 Pudovkin, A.I., Zaykin, D.V., Hedgecock, D. (1996) On the potential for estimating the
677 effective number of breeders from heterozygote excess in progeny. *Genetics*, **144**, 383-
678 387.

679 Ravel, S., Mahamat, M.H., Ségard, A., Argiles-Herrero, R., Bouyer, J., Rayaisse, J.-B.,
680 Solano, P., Mollo, B.G., Pèka, M., Darnas, J., Belem, A.M.G., Yoni, W., Noûs, C., De
681 Meeûs, T. (2023) Population genetics of *Glossina fuscipes fuscipes* from southern Chad.
682 *Peer Community Journal*, **3**, e31. <https://doi.org/10.24072/pcjournal.257>

683 Robertson, A. (1965) The interpretation of genotypic ratios in domestic animal populations.
684 *Animal Production*, **7**, 319-324.

685 Robertson, A., Hill, W.G. (1984) Deviations from Hardy-Weinberg proportions - Sampling
686 variances and use in estimation of inbreeding coefficients. *Genetics*, **107**, 703-718.

687 Rousset, F. (1996) Equilibrium values of measures of population subdivision for stepwise
688 mutation processes. *Genetics*, **142**, 1357-1362.

689 Rousset, F. (2004) *Genetic Structure and Selection in Subdivided Populations*. Princeton
690 University Press, Princeton.

691 Vitalis, R. (2002) Estim 1.2-2: a computer program to infer population parameters from
692 one- and two-locus gene identity probabilities, updated from Vitalis and Couvet (2001),
693 *Molecular Ecology Notes*, **1**, 354-356, Available at <http://www.t-de->
694 [meeus.fr/ProgMeeusGB.html](http://www.t-de-meeus.fr/ProgMeeusGB.html). <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-8278.2001.00086.x>

695 Vitalis, R., Couvet, D. (2001a) ESTIM 1.0: a computer program to infer population
696 parameters from one- and two-locus gene identity probabilities. *Molecular Ecology Notes*,
697 **1**, 354-356. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1471-8278.2001.00086.x>

698 Vitalis, R., Couvet, D. (2001b) Estimation of effective population size and migration rate
699 from one- and two-locus identity measures. *Genetics*, **157**, 911-925.

700 Vitalis, R., Couvet, D. (2001c) Two-locus identity probabilities and identity disequilibrium in
701 a partially selfing subdivided population. *Genetical Research*, **77**, 67-81.

702 Vodopivec, A. (2017) wxMaxima, a document based interface for the computer algebra
703 system Maxima, distributed under the GPL license, donwloadable at [https://wxmaxima-](https://wxmaxima-developers.github.io/wxmaxima/)
704 [developers.github.io/wxmaxima/](https://wxmaxima-developers.github.io/wxmaxima/). **version 17.10.1**.

705 Wang, J.L. (2009) A new method for estimating effective population sizes from a single
706 sample of multilocus genotypes. *Molecular Ecology*, **18**, 2148-2164. 10.1111/j.1365-
707 294X.2009.04175.x

708 Wang, J.L. (2016) A comparison of single-sample estimators of effective population sizes
709 from genetic marker data. *Molecular Ecology*, **25**, 4692-4711. 10.1111/mec.13725

710 Wang, J.L., Whitlock, M.C. (2003) Estimating effective population size and migration rates
711 from genetic samples over space and time. *Genetics*, **163**, 429-446.
712 <https://doi.org/10.1093/genetics/163.1.429>

713 Waples, R.S. (2006) A bias correction for estimates of effective population size based on
714 linkage disequilibrium at unlinked gene loci. *Conservation Genetics*, **7**, 167-184.
715 0.1007/s10592-005-9100-y

716 Waples, R.S., Do, C. (2010) Linkage disequilibrium estimates of contemporary N_e using
717 highly variable genetic markers: a largely untapped resource for applied conservation and
718 evolution. *Evolutionary Applications*, **3**, 244-262. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-4571.2009.00104.x)
719 [4571.2009.00104.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1752-4571.2009.00104.x)

720 Waples, R.S., England, P.R. (2011) Estimating contemporary effective population size on
721 the basis of linkage disequilibrium in the face of migration. *Genetics*, **189**, 633-644.
722 10.1534/genetics.111.132233

723 Weinberg, W. (1908) Über den Nachweis der Verebung beim Menschen. *Jahresheft des*
724 *Vereins für Vaterländische Naturkunde in Württemberg*, **64**, 368-382.
725 <https://archive.org/details/b30613000/page/370/mode/2up>

726 Weir, B.S., Cockerham, C.C. (1984) Estimating F-statistics for the analysis of population
727 structure. *Evolution*, **38**, 1358-1370. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1984.tb05657.x>

728 Werren, J.H. (1980) Sex ratio adaptations to local mate competition in a parasitic wasp.
729 *Science*, **208**, 1157-1159. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.208.4448.1157>

730 Wright, S. (1965) The interpretation of population structure by F-statistics with special
731 regard to system of mating. *Evolution*, **19**, 395-420. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1965.tb01731.x)
732 [5646.1965.tb01731.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1558-5646.1965.tb01731.x)

733 Wright, S. (1969) *Evolution and the genetics of Populations Volume 2: The Theory of*
734 *Gene Frequencies*. The University of Chicago Press, Chicago.

735

736

737

738

Appendices

739

740 **Appendix 1: Matrix multiplication, identity matrix, matrix determinant and matrix**
 741 **inversion.**

742 By convention, matrices and vectors appear in bold, while scalars write in italics,
 743 and matrix multiplication is noted by a point.

744 Let matrix **A** and vector **x** be:

$$745 \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \text{ and } \mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

746 Multiplying **A** by **x** yields a new vector:

$$747 \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{x} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ax_1 + bx_2 \\ cx_1 + dx_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

748

(A1-1)

749 With $\mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix}$, then:

$$750 \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ae + bg & af + bh \\ ce + dg & cf + dh \end{pmatrix}$$

751

(A1-2)

752 Please, note that most of the time $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B} \neq \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{A}$, since:

$$753 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} e & f \\ g & h \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} ae + cf & de + df \\ ag + ch & cg + dh \end{pmatrix}.$$

754

755 The identity matrix **I** must verify:

$$756 \begin{cases} \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{I} = \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{x} \end{cases}$$

757

(A1-3)

$$758 \text{ Let } \mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} I_{11} & I_{12} \\ I_{21} & I_{22} \end{pmatrix}.$$

759 Then:

$$760 \quad \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} I_{11} & I_{12} \\ I_{21} & I_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

761 \Leftrightarrow

$$762 \quad \begin{pmatrix} aI_{11} + bI_{21} & aI_{12} + bI_{22} \\ cI_{11} + dI_{21} & cI_{12} + dI_{22} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$$

763 \Leftrightarrow

$$764 \quad \begin{cases} aI_{11} + bI_{21} = a \\ aI_{12} + bI_{22} = b \\ cI_{11} + dI_{21} = c \\ cI_{12} + dI_{22} = d \end{cases}$$

765 \Leftrightarrow

$$766 \quad \begin{cases} I_{11} = \frac{a - bI_{21}}{a} \\ I_{12} = \frac{b(1 - I_{22})}{a} \\ c \frac{a - bI_{21}}{a} + dI_{21} = c \\ c \frac{b(1 - I_{22})}{a} + dI_{22} = d \end{cases}$$

767 \Leftrightarrow

$$768 \quad \begin{cases} I_{11} = \frac{a - bI_{21}}{a} \\ I_{12} = \frac{b(1 - I_{22})}{a} \\ I_{21} \left(d - \frac{bc}{a} \right) = c - \frac{ca}{a} \\ I_{22} \left(d - \frac{bc}{a} \right) = d - \frac{bc}{a} \end{cases}$$

769 (A1-4)

770 For $a \neq 0$, then equation A1-4 writes:

$$771 \quad \begin{cases} I_{11} = \frac{a - bI_{21}}{a} \\ I_{12} = \frac{b(1 - I_{22})}{a} \\ I_{21} \left(\frac{ad - bc}{a} \right) = 0 \\ I_{22} \left(\frac{ad - bc}{a} \right) = \frac{ad - bc}{a} \end{cases}$$

772 \Leftrightarrow

773

$$\begin{cases} I_{11} = \frac{a - bI_{21}}{a} \\ I_{12} = \frac{b(1 - I_{22})}{a} \\ I_{21}(ad - bc) = 0 \\ I_{22} = \frac{ad - bc}{ad - bc} \end{cases}$$

774

(A1-5)

775

Expression $ad-bc$ is the determinant of matrix \mathbf{A} , $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A})$. Equation A1-5 has a solution only

776

if $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A}) \neq 0$, in which case A1-5 writes:

777

$$\begin{cases} I_{11} = 1 \\ I_{12} = 0 \\ I_{21} = 0 \\ I_{22} = 1 \end{cases}$$

778

\Leftrightarrow

779

$$\mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

780

From there, it is easy to understand that the identity matrix of any dimension n is a

781

squared matrix with diagonal numbers equal to 1 and others to 0:

782

$$\mathbf{I}_n = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \cdots & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

783

$$\text{For } n=3, \mathbf{I}_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

784

We now have the tools to find the inverse of matrix \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{A}^{-1} , which must verify

785

$\mathbf{A}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{I}$. If we set $\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ \gamma & \delta \end{pmatrix}$, we can write:

786

$$\begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \beta \\ \gamma & \delta \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

787

\Leftrightarrow

788

$$\begin{cases} \alpha a + \beta c = 1 \\ \alpha b + \beta d = 0 \\ \gamma a + \delta c = 0 \\ \gamma b + \delta d = 1 \end{cases}$$

789

\Leftrightarrow

$$790 \quad \begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} \\ \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} b + \beta d = 0 \\ \gamma = -\frac{\delta c}{a} \\ -\frac{\delta c}{a} b + \delta d = 1 \end{cases}$$

791 \Leftrightarrow

$$792 \quad \begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} \\ \beta \left(d - \frac{bc}{a} \right) = -\frac{b}{a} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\delta c}{a} \\ \delta \left(d - \frac{cb}{a} \right) = 1 \end{cases}$$

793 \Leftrightarrow

$$794 \quad \begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} \\ \beta \left(d - \frac{bc}{a} \right) = \frac{-\frac{b}{a}}{\frac{ad - bc}{a}} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\delta c}{a} \\ \delta \left(d - \frac{cb}{a} \right) = \frac{1}{\frac{ad - bc}{a}} \end{cases}$$

795 \Leftrightarrow

$$796 \quad \begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} \\ \beta = \frac{-\frac{b}{a}}{\frac{ad - bc}{a}} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\delta c}{a} \\ \delta = \frac{1}{\frac{ad - bc}{a}} \end{cases}$$

797

(A1-6)

798 For $a \neq 0$, equation A1-6 becomes:

799

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 - \beta c}{a} \\ \beta = \frac{-b}{ad - bc} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\delta c}{a} \\ \delta = \frac{a}{ad - bc} \end{cases}$$

800 \Leftrightarrow

801

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{1 + \frac{b}{ad - bc}c}{a} \\ \beta = \frac{-b}{ad - bc} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\frac{a}{ad - bc}c}{a} \\ \delta = \frac{a}{ad - bc} \end{cases}$$

802 \Leftrightarrow

803

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{\frac{ad - bc + bc}{ad - bc}}{a} \\ \beta = \frac{-b}{ad - bc} \\ \gamma = -\frac{\frac{ac}{ad - bc}}{a} \\ \delta = \frac{a}{ad - bc} \end{cases}$$

804 \Leftrightarrow

805

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = \frac{d}{ad - bc} \\ \beta = \frac{-b}{ad - bc} \\ \gamma = \frac{-c}{ad - bc} \\ \delta = \frac{a}{ad - bc} \end{cases}$$

806 Consequently, the reverse of matrix \mathbf{A} is:

807

$$\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \frac{1}{ad - bc} \begin{pmatrix} d & -b \\ -c & a \end{pmatrix}$$

808 We know that $ad - bc = \text{Det}(\mathbf{A})$, thus:

809
$$\mathbf{A}^{-1} = \frac{1}{\text{Det}(\mathbf{A})} \begin{pmatrix} d & -b \\ -c & a \end{pmatrix}$$

810 (A1-7)

811 When $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A})=0$, \mathbf{A} is singular. When $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A})\neq 0$, \mathbf{A} is nonsingular. A nonsingular
812 matrix is necessarily squared.

813 To compute the inverse of a 3×3 matrix, it is easier using a mathematical software
814 as Maxima (Vodopivec, 2017) (command `invert(A)`).

815

816 **Appendix 2: eigenvalues and eigenvectors**

817 For the sake of space saving and simplicity, we will take the example of a 2×2
818 matrix \mathbf{X} and a two lines column vector \mathbf{e} :

819
$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{X} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e} = \begin{pmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

820 If λ_i is an eigenvalue and \mathbf{e}_i the corresponding eigenvector of matrix \mathbf{X} , then they must
821 satisfy the equation: $\mathbf{X}.\mathbf{e}_i=\lambda_i.\mathbf{e}_i$. We can translate this into the system of equations:

822
$$\begin{cases} x_{11} \times e_1 + x_{12} \times e_2 = \lambda e_1 \\ x_{21} \times e_1 + x_{22} \times e_2 = \lambda e_2 \end{cases}$$

823 Excluding the trivial solution where $\mathbf{e}_1=\mathbf{e}_2=0$, we can rewrite the preceding equations as:

824
$$\begin{cases} x_{11} + x_{12} \times \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \lambda \\ x_{21} + x_{22} \times \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \lambda \frac{e_2}{e_1} \end{cases}$$

825 \Leftrightarrow

826
$$\begin{cases} x_{11} + x_{12} \times \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \lambda \\ x_{21} = \frac{e_2}{e_1} (\lambda - x_{22}) \end{cases}$$

827 \Leftrightarrow

$$828 \quad \begin{cases} x_{11} + x_{12} \times \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \lambda \\ \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} = \frac{e_2}{e_1} \end{cases}$$

829 \Leftrightarrow

$$830 \quad \begin{cases} x_{11} + x_{12} \times \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} = \lambda \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

831 \Leftrightarrow

$$832 \quad \begin{cases} \frac{(\lambda - x_{22})x_{11} + x_{12} \times x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} = \lambda \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

833 \Leftrightarrow

$$834 \quad \begin{cases} x_{11} \times \lambda - x_{11}x_{22} + x_{12} \times x_{21} = \lambda^2 - x_{22} \times \lambda \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

835 \Leftrightarrow

$$836 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda^2 - (x_{11} + x_{22}) \times \lambda = -x_{11}x_{22} + x_{12} \times x_{21} \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

837 \Leftrightarrow

$$838 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda^2 - x_{11} \times \lambda - x_{22} \times \lambda + x_{11}x_{22} - x_{12} \times x_{21} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

839 \Leftrightarrow

$$840 \quad \begin{cases} -\lambda(x_{11} - \lambda) + x_{22}(x_{11} - \lambda) - x_{21} \times x_{12} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

841 \Leftrightarrow

$$842 \quad \begin{cases} (x_{11} - \lambda)(x_{22} - \lambda) - x_{21} \times x_{12} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

843

(A2-1)

844 Knowing that the determinant of a matrix \mathbf{A} $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A}) = \text{Det} \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} = ad - cd$, Eq A2-1 writes:

$$845 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Det} \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} - \lambda & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} - \lambda \end{pmatrix} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

846 \Leftrightarrow

$$847 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Det} \left(\begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} \lambda & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda \end{pmatrix} \right) = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

848 \Leftrightarrow

$$849 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Det} \left(\begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{pmatrix} - \lambda \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \right) = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

850 (A2-2)

851 The matrix $\mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is called the identity matrix (Appendix 1).

852 The first line of EqA2-2 writes $\text{Det}(\mathbf{A}) - \lambda \cdot \mathbf{I} = 0$ and corresponds to the so called characteristic
853 equation of matrix \mathbf{A} . We can solve EqA2-2:

$$854 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Det} \left(\begin{pmatrix} x_{11} - \lambda & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} - \lambda \end{pmatrix} \right) = 0 \\ \frac{x_2}{x_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

855 \Leftrightarrow

$$856 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (x_{11} - \lambda)(x_{22} - \lambda) - x_{21}x_{12} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

857 \Leftrightarrow

$$858 \quad \begin{cases} -\lambda x_{11} - \lambda x_{22} + \lambda^2 + x_{11}x_{22} - x_{21}x_{12} = 0 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

859 \Leftrightarrow

$$860 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda^2 - 2\lambda \frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22}) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2 = -(x_{11}x_{22} - x_{21}x_{12}) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

861 \Leftrightarrow

$$862 \quad \begin{cases} \left[\lambda - \frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2 = -\text{Det}(A) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2 \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

863 \Leftrightarrow

$$864 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda - \frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22}) = \mp \sqrt{-\text{Det}(A) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2} \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

865 \Leftrightarrow

$$866 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda = \frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22}) \mp \sqrt{-\text{Det}(A) + \left[\frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22})\right]^2} \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

867 \Leftrightarrow

$$868 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda = \frac{1}{2}(x_{11} + x_{22}) \mp \sqrt{-x_{11}x_{22} + x_{21}x_{12} + \frac{1}{4}(x_{11}^2 + x_{22}^2 + 2x_{11}x_{22})} \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{cases}$$

869 \Leftrightarrow

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda = \frac{(x_{11} + x_{22}) \mp \sqrt{x_{11}^2 + x_{22}^2 + 4x_{21}x_{12} - 2x_{11}x_{22}}}{2} \\ \frac{e_2}{e_1} = \frac{x_{21}}{\lambda - x_{22}} \end{array} \right.$$

871 (A2-3)

872 We have two eigenvalues:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_1 = \frac{x_{11} + x_{22} + \sqrt{x_{11}^2 + x_{22}^2 + 4x_{21}x_{12} - 2x_{11}x_{22}}}{2} \\ \lambda_2 = \frac{x_{11} + x_{22} - \sqrt{x_{11}^2 + x_{22}^2 + 4x_{21}x_{12} - 2x_{11}x_{22}}}{2} \end{array} \right.$$

874 (A2-4)

875 Note that a solution exists only if $\lambda \neq x_{ii}$ ($i=1$ or 2), and if $e_1 \neq 0$ or $e_2 \neq 0$. For a 2×2 matrix, if a
 876 solution exists for its characteristic equation, it has two eigenvalues, i.e. the same number
 877 as the dimension of the matrix: λ_1 and λ_2 . For each eigenvalue, we can find an infinite
 878 collection of of eigenvectors that all satisfy:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_{11} \times e_1 + x_{12} \times e_2 = \lambda e_1 \\ x_{21} \times e_1 + x_{22} \times e_2 = \lambda e_2 \end{array} \right.$$

880 \Leftrightarrow

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (x_{11} - \lambda) \times e_1 = -x_{12} \times e_2 \\ (x_{22} - \lambda) \times e_2 = -x_{21} \times e_1 \end{array} \right.$$

882 \Leftrightarrow

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} e_2 = -\frac{(x_{11} - \lambda)}{x_{12}} \times e_1 \\ (x_{22} - \lambda) \times e_2 = -x_{21} \times e_1 \end{array} \right.$$

884 Then, for $e_1=1$, a first pair of eigenvectors would be:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_1 - x_{11} \\ x_{12} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_2 - x_{11} \\ x_{12} \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

886 (A2-5)

887 We can go back to EqA2-2 to obtain eigenvalues as function of x_{21} (as is the case in
888 certain textbooks), this leads to:

$$889 \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\lambda_1 - x_{22}}{x_{21}} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\lambda_2 - x_{22}}{x_{21}} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

890

891 **Appendix 3: Matrix power and diagonalization**

892 Computing matrix powers is difficult, except for diagonal matrices. Indeed, using
893 equation A1-2, it is easy to see that:

$$894 \quad \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & d \end{pmatrix}^2 = \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a^2 + 0 & 0 + 0 \\ 0 + 0 & 0 + d^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

895 \Leftrightarrow

$$896 \quad \begin{pmatrix} a & 0 \\ 0 & d \end{pmatrix}^t = \begin{pmatrix} a^t & 0 \\ 0 & d^t \end{pmatrix}$$

897 (A3-1)

898 For any other squared matrix **A**, it may thus be useful to diagonalize it, if one wants
899 to compute any power of it. In Horn and Johnson's book, page 59 (Horn & Johnson, 2013),
900 we are invited to solve the equation:

$$901 \quad \mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{D},$$

902 (A3-2)

903 where **P** is an invertible matrix and **D** a diagonal matrix.

904 Let **A**, **P** and **D**, \mathbf{v}_1 and \mathbf{v}_2 be:

905

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{P} = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{D} = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{v}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} \\ p_{21} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{v}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} p_{12} \\ p_{22} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

906 We can also write $\mathbf{P}=(\mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_2)$. We can thus rewrite equation A(3.2) as:

907

$$\mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_2) = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

908 \Leftrightarrow

909

$$\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_2) = \mathbf{P} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

910 \Leftrightarrow

911

$$\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot (\mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{v}_2) = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

912 \Leftrightarrow

913

$$(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_2) = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 \cdot p_{11} & \lambda_2 \cdot p_{12} \\ \lambda_1 \cdot p_{21} & \lambda_2 \cdot p_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

914 \Leftrightarrow

915

$$(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 \ \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_2) = (\lambda_1 \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 \ \lambda_2 \cdot \mathbf{v}_2)$$

916 \Leftrightarrow

917

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 = \lambda_1 \cdot \mathbf{v}_1 \\ \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v}_2 = \lambda_2 \cdot \mathbf{v}_2 \end{cases}$$

918 We recognize what we saw about eigenvalues and eigenvectors in Appendix 2,

919 meaning that matrix \mathbf{S} is a combination of eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} , and \mathbf{D} is a diagonal matrix920 with matrix \mathbf{A} 's eigenvalues on the diagonal from the bigger (top left) to the smallest

921 (bottom right).

922 From there, computing the power of any matrix **A** is relatively easy. Indeed, if we
 923 have $\mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{D}$, then this also writes $\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{A} = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}$. From there,
 924 computing \mathbf{A}^t is easy:

925
$$\mathbf{A}^t = (\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}) \cdot (\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}) \cdot (\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}) \cdot (\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}) \dots (\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1})$$

926 \Leftrightarrow

927
$$\mathbf{A}^t = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot (\mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{P}) \dots (\mathbf{P}^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{P}) \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}$$

928 \Leftrightarrow

929
$$\mathbf{A}^t = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{I} \dots \mathbf{I} \cdot \mathbf{D} \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}$$

930 where **I** is the identity matrix. From there, we can compute:

931
$$\mathbf{A}^t = \mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{D}^t \cdot \mathbf{P}^{-1}$$

932 (A3-3)

933 Consequently, we can use equation (A3-3) to calculate the power of any diagonalizable
 934 square matrix.

935 We can now derive some other properties of eigenvalue-eigenvector pairs
 936 (eigenpairs).

937 For the 2x2 matrix **A**, with the eigenpairs λ_i and \mathbf{e}_i , where *i* stands for 1 or 2,

938 $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i = \lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$. Then $\mathbf{A}^2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_i = \mathbf{A} \cdot (\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i) = \mathbf{A} \cdot (\lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i) = \lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i = \lambda_i^2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$. It follows that:

939
$$\mathbf{A}^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_i = \lambda_i^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

940 (A3-4)

941 Let **v** be a vector composed of a combination of eigenvectors of matrix **A** so that

942 $\mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$, where the *x*'s are scalars that can be computed. We can then write:

943
$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \sum_i x_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

944 \Leftrightarrow

945
$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i = \sum_i x_i \cdot \lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

946 \Leftrightarrow

947
$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \mathbf{A} \cdot \sum_i x_i \cdot \lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

948 \Leftrightarrow

949
$$\mathbf{A}^2 \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot \lambda_i^2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

950 \Leftrightarrow

951
$$\mathbf{A}^t \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot \lambda_i^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

952 (A3-5)

953 This property can be used to any power function of matrices. In particular, for the
 954 matrix $\mathbf{S}=(\mathbf{I}-\gamma \cdot \mathbf{A})$, which should be invertible, it is easy to see that the eigenpairs of \mathbf{S} are (in
 955 decreasing order of the hierarchy) $\lambda_1'=1-\gamma \lambda_2$, $\mathbf{e}_1'=\mathbf{e}_2$ and $\lambda_2'=1-\gamma \lambda_1$, $\mathbf{e}_2'=\mathbf{e}_1$. Indeed, if we take
 956 the eigenvector \mathbf{e}_i , then: $\mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i=\mathbf{e}_i-\gamma \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i=\mathbf{e}_i-\gamma \cdot \lambda_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i=(\mathbf{I}-\gamma \cdot \lambda_i) \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$ (QED).

957 Using equation A3-5, we can write:

958
$$\mathbf{S}^t \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot (1 - \gamma \lambda_i)^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

959 This logically yields:

960
$$(\mathbf{I} - \gamma \mathbf{A})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot (1 - \gamma \lambda_i)^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

961 \Leftrightarrow

962
$$(\mathbf{I} - \gamma \mathbf{A})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{v} = \sum_i \frac{1}{1 - \gamma \lambda_i} \cdot x_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

963 (A3-6)

964 Equation A3-6 corresponds to equation A.10 of Rousset's book (page 219), which
 965 was given without any detailed proof.

966

967 **Appendix 4: eigenvalue effective population size**

968 This notion refers to the evolution of heterozygosity, or more exactly genetic
 969 diversity, defined as the probability, at generation t , to draw randomly two alleles that are

970 not identical by descent, from one generation to the other, and labelled H_{t-1} and H_t . If the
 971 evolution of a population by genetic drift has reached a steady state, the ratio of H_t/H_{t-1}
 972 remains constant generation after generation and has been shown to correspond to the
 973 leading eigenvalue of the transition matrix for the evolution of vectors of genetic identity
 974 probabilities (see below).

975 Let Q_I be the probability of identity within diploid individuals, and Q_S , the probability
 976 of identity between two alleles from two individuals of the same population. In an ideal
 977 population of size N , and thus under panmixia (thus here $Q_I=Q_S$), we can set the system of
 978 equations:

$$979 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I_{t-1}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} \\ Q_{S_t} = \frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I_{t-1}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} \end{cases}$$

980 \Leftrightarrow

$$981 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \frac{1}{2N} Q_{S_{t-1}} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N} \\ Q_{S_t} = \frac{1}{2N} Q_{S_{t-1}} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

982 \Leftrightarrow

$$983 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N} \\ Q_{S_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

984 If we replace identities with their corresponding values in terms of genetic non-identity
 985 (hence diversity), we obtain:

$$986 \quad \begin{cases} 1 - H_{I_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right) (1 - H_{S_{t-1}}) + \frac{1}{2N} \\ 1 - H_{S_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right) (1 - H_{S_{t-1}}) + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

987 \Leftrightarrow

988
$$\begin{cases} H_{I_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right) H_{S_{t-1}} \\ H_{S_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right) H_{S_{t-1}} \end{cases}$$

989 (A4-1)

990 Assuming a steady state, so that $H_{S_t}/H_{S_{t-1}}=H_{S_{t-1}}/H_{S_{t-2}}=\lambda$, we can set:

991
$$\lambda = 1 - \frac{1}{2N}$$

992 Let us now define the vector \mathbf{H}_t and transition matrix \mathbf{A} , as:

993
$$\mathbf{H}_t = \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix}$$

994
$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}$$

995 Using these, equation A1-1 also writes: $\mathbf{H}_t = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{H}_{t-1} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{H}_t = \mathbf{A}^2 \cdot \mathbf{H}_{t-2} \Leftrightarrow \mathbf{H}_t = \mathbf{A}^t \cdot \mathbf{H}_0$.

996 This also writes:

997
$$\begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}^t \cdot \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_1} \\ H_{S_1} \end{pmatrix}$$

998 (A4-2)

999 were H_I and H_S are genetic diversities at time 0.

1000 We can decompose \mathbf{H}_0 as a function of eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2) (see appendix 3) and
 1001 scalars c_1 and c_2 such as:

1002
$$\begin{pmatrix} H_{I_1} \\ H_{S_1} \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2$$

1003 (A4-3)

1004 Combining Equations A4-2 and A4-3 yields:

1005
$$\begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}^t \cdot (c_1 \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \cdot \mathbf{e}_2)$$

1006 ⇔

$$1007 \quad \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_2$$

1008 (A4-4)

1009 Following what we know from the properties of eigenpairs (see Appendices 2 and 3), using
1010 equation A3-5, we can rewrite equation A4-4 as:

$$1011 \quad \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \cdot \lambda_1^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \cdot \lambda_2^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_2$$

1012 (A4-5)

1013 With eigenpairs λ_i and \mathbf{e}_i of matrix $\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ 0 & 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix}$, using EqA2-4, we can compute the

1014 two eigenvalues of matrix \mathbf{A} :

$$1015 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1 = \frac{0 + 1 - \frac{1}{2N} + \sqrt{0^2 + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^2 + 4 \times 0 \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right) - 2 \times 0 \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)}}{2} \\ \lambda_2 = \frac{0 + 1 - \frac{1}{2N} - \sqrt{0^2 + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^2 + 4 \times 0 \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right) - 2 \times 0 \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)}}{2} \end{cases}$$

1016 ⇔

$$1017 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1 = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2N} + \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^2}}{2} \\ \lambda_2 = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{2N} - \sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^2}}{2} \end{cases}$$

1018 ⇔

$$1019 \quad \begin{cases} \lambda_1 = 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \\ \lambda_2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

1020 (A4-6)

1021 For the eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} , using equation A2-5, we have:

$$1022 \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 - \frac{1}{2N} - 0 \\ 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 - 0 \\ 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

1023 \Leftrightarrow

$$1024 \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

1025 (A4-7)

1026 Combining A4-7 and A4-6 with A1-5 we can write:

$$1027 \quad \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

1028 \Leftrightarrow

$$1029 \quad \begin{cases} H_{I_t} = c_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t \\ H_{S_t} = c_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t \end{cases}$$

1030 (A4-8)

1031 From there, we can also easily see that, for any $c_1 \neq 0$:

$$1032 \quad \frac{H_{S_t}}{H_{S_{t-1}}} = \frac{c_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t}{c_1 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^{t-1}} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right) = \lambda_1$$

1033 (A4-9)

1034 The ratio of genetic diversities of generation t and $t-1$ is indeed the leading eigenvalue of
1035 the transition matrix describing the evolution of genetic diversities (and of genetic identities
1036 as well) (QED).

1037 We can also determine c_1 and c_2 , if genetic diversities at time 0 are known. From
 1038 equations A4-3 and A4-7, we know that:

$$1039 \quad \begin{cases} H_I = c_1 + c_2 \\ H_S = c_1 \end{cases}$$

1040 \Leftrightarrow

$$1041 \quad \begin{cases} c_1 = H_S \\ c_2 = H_I - H_S \end{cases}$$

1042 (A4-10)

1043 Now if we combine equations A1-8 and A1-10 we can compute, for H_S (which is here the
 1044 same as H_I):

$$1045 \quad \begin{cases} H_{I_t} = H_S \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t \\ H_{S_t} = H_S \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t \end{cases}$$

1046 This results confirms that, at any generation $H_I = H_S$, and hence $c_2 = 0$. We can then simply
 1047 write, for the Wright-Fisher model:

$$1048 \quad H_{I_t} = H_S \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N}\right)^t$$

1049 \Leftrightarrow

$$1050 \quad H_{S_t} = H_S \cdot \lambda_1^t$$

1051 (A4-11)

1052 where H_S is the local genetic diversity at time 0, and λ_1 is the leading eigenvalue of the
 1053 transition matrix \mathbf{A} .

1054 Now, for any transition matrix $\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} x_{11} & x_{12} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} \end{pmatrix}$, where the x_{ij} are probabilities (e.g. of
 1055 identity), with eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 and corresponding eigenvectors \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 (Appendix
 1056 2), we can use the same approach and obtain:

$$1057 \quad \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} = c_1 \cdot \lambda_1^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 + c_2 \cdot \lambda_2^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_2$$

1058 (A4-12)

1059 From equation A2-4, it is very easy to see that $\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = x_{11} + x_{22}$, and that $\lambda_1 > \lambda_2$. From
 1060 matrix **A** defined for the WF model, we can see that all x_{ij} are probabilities that only sum to
 1061 1 for the Castle-Weinberg model and hence $x_{11} + x_{22} \leq 1$. In the case of WF, the difference
 1062 between λ_1 and λ_2 is even very big (equation A4-6). Consequently, when t becomes big
 1063 enough $\lambda_1^t \gg \lambda_2^t$ and equation A1-12 can be approximated as:

$$1064 \begin{pmatrix} H_{I_t} \\ H_{S_t} \end{pmatrix} \approx c_1 \cdot \lambda_1^t \cdot \mathbf{e}_1$$

1065 (A4-13)

1066 Combining A4-13 with A2-5 yields:

$$1067 \begin{cases} H_{I_t} \approx c_1 \cdot \lambda_1^t \\ H_{S_t} \approx c_1 \cdot \lambda_1^t \frac{\lambda_1 - x_{11}}{x_{12}} \end{cases}$$

1068 (A1-14)

1069 From there, and for any H_X ($X=I$ or S), it is straightforward that the ratio $H_t/H_{t-1} = \lambda_1$. From
 1070 equation A4-6, we know that the leading eigenvalue of the transition matrix of a fully
 1071 panmictic model (i.e. WF) is $\lambda_e = 1 - 1/(2N_e)$ and thus, the effective population size of any
 1072 non-reference population will follow $\lambda_1 = 1 - 1/(2N_e)$, which is equivalent to:

$$1073 1 - \lambda_1 \approx \frac{1}{2N_e}$$

1074 Consequently, the eigenvalue effective population size of any population will be:

$$1075 N_e \approx \frac{1}{2(1 - \lambda_1)}$$

1076 (A4-15)

1077 where λ_1 is the leading eigenvalue of the transition matrix, describing the evolution of
 1078 genetic diversities (or same wise of genetic identities) from one generation to the other, for
 1079 that population.

1080 All these detailed explanations leading to equation A4-15 provide the same result as
 1081 equation 3.105 in Ewen's book (page 120) (Ewens, 2004), which was given with much
 1082 more elliptic explanations.

1083 It is also worth noting that equation A4-15 is only accurate when t is big enough, or
 1084 when the population has reached a steady state so that the ratio H_t/H_{t-1} becomes constant
 1085 and equal to λ_1 .

1086

1087 **Appendix 5: Pudovkin et al.'s methods to compute N_e**

1088 Let p_f and p_m be allele frequencies of one of two alleles at a given locus in females
 1089 and males respectively, in a population with an even sex-ratio. Then, in the progeny, the
 1090 proportion of heterozygotes observed should be $H_{\text{exp-dio}} = p_f(1-p_m) + (1-p_f)p_m$. In this
 1091 population, the frequency of this allele will be $(p_f + p_m)/2$. Consequently, the expected
 1092 frequency of heterozygotes under the panmictic (monoecious) model in the progeny
 1093 ($H_{\text{exp-mon}}$) would be:

1094
$$H_{\text{exp-mon}} = 2 \left(\frac{p_f + p_m}{2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{p_f + p_m}{2} \right)$$

1095 \Leftrightarrow

1096
$$H_{\text{exp-mon}} = (p_f + p_m) \left(\frac{2 - p_f - p_m}{2} \right)$$

1097 \Leftrightarrow

1098
$$H_{\text{exp-mon}} = \frac{2p_f + 2p_m - p_f^2 - p_m^2 - 2p_f p_m}{2}$$

1099 \Leftrightarrow

1100
$$H_{\text{exp-on}} = p_f + p_m - p_f p_m - \frac{p_f^2 + p_m^2}{2}$$

1101 \Leftrightarrow

1102
$$H_{\text{exp-mon}} = p_f(1 - p_m) + p_m(1 - p_f) - \frac{p_f^2 + p_m^2 - 2p_f p_m}{2}$$

1103 \Leftrightarrow

1104
$$H_{\text{exp-mon}} = H_{\text{exp-dio}} - \frac{(p_f - p_m)^2}{2}$$

1105 ⇔

1106
$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_{\text{exp-mon}} + \frac{(p_f - p_m)^2}{2}$$

1107 (A5-1)

1108 Please note that $H_{\text{exp-dio}}$ and $H_{\text{exp-mon}}$ here correspond to H_{obs} and H_{exp} respectively
 1109 in (Pudovkin et al., 1996). There is thus an observed heterozygote excess in the progeny.

1110 The quantity $p_f - p_m$ can be considered as a random variable with average 0 over all
 1111 possible parental groups. If we consider that the frequency of the first allele was p in the
 1112 parental population, then the average of $(p_f - p_m)^2$ is the variance of a difference in allele
 1113 frequencies between two binomial samples of size N for each gender (N alleles in females
 1114 and N in males= $2N$ alleles in total). The variance of frequency of a given allele randomly
 1115 taken in a population of size N , is $p(1-p)/N$, where p is the frequency of the allele in the
 1116 parents. The variance of a difference between two uncorrelated (e.g. independent) random
 1117 variables is the sum of individual variances (see the file VarDif.pdf), here $p(1-p)/(N)+p(1-$
 1118 $p)/(N)=2p(1-p)/N$. Equation (A5-1), for the entire space of possible outcomes can thus
 1119 write:

1120
$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_{\text{exp-mon}} + \frac{p(1-p)}{N}$$

1121 (A5-2)

1122 If we replace $p(1-p)$ as $H_{\text{exp-mon}}/2$, N by N_e and rearrange equation (A5-2), one obtains:

1123
$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_{\text{exp-mon}} + \frac{H_{\text{exp-mon}}}{2N_e}$$

1124
$$-\frac{H_{\text{exp-mon}}}{2N_e} = H_{\text{exp-mon}} - H_{\text{exp-dio}}$$

1125 ⇔

1126

$$N_e = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{H_{\text{exp-mon}}}{H_{\text{exp-mon}} - H_{\text{obsexp-dio}}}$$

1127

(A5-3)

1128

The parametric formula of Wright's F_{IS} can be written as (Nei & Chesser, 1983):

1129

$$F_{IS} = \frac{H_{\text{exp}} - H_{\text{obs}}}{H_{\text{exp}}}$$

1130

(A5-4)

1131

If we combine equations (A5-3) and (A5-4), replacing H_{exp} with $H_{\text{exp-mon}}$ and H_{obs} with $H_{\text{exp-dio}}$,

1132

we obtain the same result (with F_{IS}) as equation (3) in Pudovkin et al.'s paper (if we

1133

replace F_{IS} by $-D$):

1134

$$N_e = -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}}$$

1135

(A5-5)

1136

In their appendix, Pudovkin et al. then used a sleight of hand. They set $N=N_e$ again, $2p(1-$

1137

$p)=H_{t-1}$ and $H_{\text{exp-mon}}=H_t$, and used the equation $\lambda=H_t/H_{t-1}$, citing Kimura and Crow's book

1138

(Crow & Kimura, 1970). Then, with $p(1-p)=H_{t-1}/2$, $H_{t-1}=H_t/\lambda$ and $H_{\text{exp}}=H_t$, we can rewrite A5-

1139

2:

1140

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_t + \frac{H_{t-1}}{2N_e}$$

1141

⇔

1142

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_t + H_t \frac{1}{2\lambda N_e}$$

1143

⇔

1144

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_t \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\lambda N_e} \right)$$

1145

(A5-6)

1146

Pudovkin et al. used another sleight of hand from equation 3.11.8 (page 104) from Crow

1147

and Kimura's book (Crow & Kimura, 1970), replacing subpopulation sizes N by N_e (again)

1148

and obtained:

1149

$$\lambda = \frac{N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}}{2N_e}$$

1150

(A5-7)

1151

The way Pudovkin et al used this equation may be inaccurate because Crow and

1152

Kimura's equation refers to the number of individuals, not the effective population size.

1153

Nevertheless, if we combine equations A5-6 and A5-7 we obtain:

1154

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_t \left(1 + \frac{1}{2 \frac{N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}}{2N_e} N_e} \right)$$

1155

⇔

1156

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} = H_t \left(1 + \frac{1}{N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}} \right)$$

1157

⇔

1158

$$H_{\text{exp-dio}} - H_t = H_t \left(1 + \frac{1}{N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}} - 1 \right)$$

1159

⇔

1160

$$\frac{H_{\text{exp-dio}} - H_t}{H_t} = \frac{1}{2N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}}$$

1161

(A5-8)

1162

From equation A5-4, and setting that H_t is the expected heterozygote frequency in the

1163

progeny, hence $H_{\text{exp-mon}}$, we can rewrite equation A5-8 as:

1164

$$-F_{\text{IS}} = \frac{1}{N_e - 1 + \sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}}$$

1165

⇔

1166
$$-F_{IS}N_e + F_{IS} - F_{IS}\sqrt{N_e^2 + 1} = 1$$

1167 \Leftrightarrow

1168
$$-F_{IS}N_e + F_{IS} - 1 = F_{IS}\sqrt{N_e^2 + 1}$$

1169 \Leftrightarrow

1170
$$(-F_{IS}N_e + F_{IS} - 1)(-F_{IS}N_e + F_{IS} - 1) = F_{IS}^2(N_e^2 + 1)$$

1171 \Leftrightarrow

1172
$$F_{IS}^2N_e^2 - F_{IS}^2N_e + F_{IS}N_e - F_{IS}^2N_e + F_{IS}^2 - F_{IS} + F_{IS}N_e - F_{IS} + 1 - F_{IS}^2N_e^2 - F_{IS}^2 = 0$$

1173 \Leftrightarrow

1174
$$-2F_{IS}^2N_e + 2F_{IS}N_e - 2F_{IS} + 1 = 0$$

1175 \Leftrightarrow

1176
$$2F_{IS}N_e(1 - F_{IS}) = 2F_{IS} - 1$$

1177 \Leftrightarrow

1178
$$N_e = -\frac{1 - 2F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}(1 - F_{IS})}$$

1179 \Leftrightarrow

1180
$$N_e = -\frac{1 - F_{IS} - F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}(1 - F_{IS})}$$

1181 \Leftrightarrow

1182
$$N_e = -\frac{1 - F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}(1 - F_{IS})} + \frac{F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}(1 - F_{IS})}$$

1183 \Leftrightarrow

1184
$$N_e = -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}} + \frac{1}{2(1 - F_{IS})}$$

1185 (A5-9)

1186 Considering that $F_{IS}=-D$, we get:

1187
$$N_e = \frac{1}{2D} + \frac{1}{2(D + 1)}$$

1188 (A5-10)

1189 Equation A5-10 is the same Pudovkin et al's (Pudovkin et al., 1996) equation 4:

1190

1191 **Appendix 6: Coalescent effective population size in a dioecious pangamic**

1192 **population**

1193 Let Q_I and Q_S be the probabilities that the same allele is sampled twice, either in
1194 one individual or in two distinct individuals from the same population. Let u be the mutation
1195 rate per generation in an infinite allele model where each mutation event produces a new
1196 allele that never existed before (no homoplasy). Then, for a dioecious population with an
1197 even sex-ratio and random mating, we can set the following recurrences between
1198 generation t and $t-1$ (Equations 7 and 8 with an even sex-ratio and mutation rate u) (see
1199 equations 7 and 8 with $N_f=N_m$).

$$1200 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = (1-u)^2 Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = (1-u)^2 \left[\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] \end{cases}$$

1201 \Leftrightarrow

$$1202 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = (1-u)^2 Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = (1-u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} Q_{I(t-1)} + (1-u)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} + (1-u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

1203 (A6-1)

1204 Let \mathbf{Q}_t the vector of genetic identities at time t and \mathbf{A} be the squared matrix of transition for
1205 genetic identities, \mathbf{v} the corresponding vector of residuals, and \mathbf{I} the identity matrix. If $\gamma=(1-$
1206 $u)^2$ is the probability that two alleles taken at random did not mutate, then we can write:

$$1207 \quad \mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1208 (A6-2)

1209 For the example of a dioecious population with even sex ratio this would yield (see
1210 equation A6-1):

1211

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{Q}_t = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{I(t)} \\ Q_{S(t)} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2N} & \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right) \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{v} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

1212

(A6-3)

1213 Equation A6-2 is equivalent to:

1214

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma \mathbf{A} (\gamma \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}_{t-2} + \gamma \mathbf{v}) + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1215 \Leftrightarrow

1216

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma^2 \mathbf{A}^2 \mathbf{Q}_{t-2} + \gamma^2 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1217 \Leftrightarrow

1218

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma^2 \mathbf{A}^2 (\gamma \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q}_{t-3} + \gamma \mathbf{v}) + \gamma^2 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1219 \Leftrightarrow

1220

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma^3 \mathbf{A}^3 \mathbf{Q}_{t-3} + \gamma^3 \mathbf{A}^2 \mathbf{v} + \gamma^2 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1221 \Leftrightarrow

1222

$$\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma^{(t-1)} \mathbf{A}^{(t-1)} \mathbf{Q}_1 + \gamma^{(t-1)} \mathbf{A}^{(t-2)} \mathbf{v} + \gamma^{(t-2)} \mathbf{A}^{(t-3)} \mathbf{v} + \dots + \gamma^2 \mathbf{A} \mathbf{v} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1223 Assuming that equilibrium values has been reached at time t ($t \rightarrow \infty$):

1224

$$\mathbf{Q} = \gamma^{(t-1)} \mathbf{A}^{(t-1)} \mathbf{Q}_1 + \left(\sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^t \mathbf{A}^{(t-1)} \mathbf{v} \right)$$

1225

(A6-4)

1226

1227

1228

1229

1230

1231

We can see that the second term in these equations will increase with t , albeit at a diminishing rate, while the first term will decrease with t . Hence, if inbreeding within individuals and within subpopulation are small enough at time $t=1$, after a sufficient number of generations, and using equation A3-5 and decomposing \mathbf{v} as $\mathbf{v} = \sum_i x_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$, where the x 's are scalars that can be computed and \mathbf{e}_i are eigenvectors of \mathbf{A} , we can approximate equation A6-4 as:

1232

$$\mathbf{Q} \approx \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^t \sum_i \lambda_i^{(t-1)} x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1233

(A6-5)

1234

This is the same as the second part of equation 4.10 in Rousset's book, page 56 (Rousset,

1235

2004). It is worthy of note that such an approximation is invalid in populations with poor

1236

levels of genetic diversity in the first generations.

1237

We can also compute \mathbf{Q} at equilibrium. For this we set equation A6-2 as:

1238

$$\mathbf{Q} = \gamma \mathbf{A} \mathbf{Q} + \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1239

\Leftrightarrow

1240

$$\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{I} - \gamma \mathbf{A}) = \gamma \mathbf{v}$$

1241

\Leftrightarrow

1242

$$\mathbf{Q} = \gamma (\mathbf{I} - \gamma \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{v}$$

1243

(A6-6)

1244

We can use equation A3-6 to obtain:

1245

$$\mathbf{Q} = \gamma \sum_i \frac{1}{1 - \gamma \lambda_i} \cdot x_i \cdot \mathbf{e}_i$$

1246

(A6-7)

1247

This equation corresponds to the first part of equation 4.10 given in Rousset's book.

1248

We can also express \mathbf{Q} as a function of probability of pairwise coalescence at time

1249

t . If we define a vector \mathbf{C}_t of such probabilities within individuals and between individuals

1250

(to stick to our framework with two hierarchies), we can write:

1251

$$\mathbf{C}_t = \begin{pmatrix} C_{I(t)} \\ C_{S(t)} \end{pmatrix}$$

1252

(A6-8)

1253

In equation A6-8, $C_{I(t)}$ and $C_{S(t)}$ are the probabilities, at time t , that two alleles of one

1254

individual (I) or of different individuals in the subpopulation (S), respectively, all randomly

1255

chosen, had coalesced somewhere in the past. At equilibrium, or after a lot of generations,

1256 identities will correspond to the sum of all coalescent events that occurred in the past, and
 1257 if no mutation ever occurred, and hence:

$$1258 \quad \mathbf{Q} = \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \mathbf{C}_t \gamma^t$$

1259 (A6-9)

1260 Combining equations A6-5 and A6-9 provides the following equality:

$$1261 \quad \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^t \sum_i \lambda_i^{(t-1)} x_i \mathbf{e}_i \approx \sum_{t=1}^{\infty} \gamma^t \mathbf{C}_t$$

1262 This means that:

$$1263 \quad \mathbf{C}_t \approx \sum_i \lambda_i^{(t-1)} x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1264 (A6-10)

1265 This equation meets with equation 4.11 page 56 in Rousset's book (Rousset, 2004).

1266 The mean coalescent time between two alleles in hierarchy J $T_{J(t)}$ (J=I or S for the
 1267 example treated in the present paper) at time t , can be computed as the sum of the products
 1268 of the time of each event of coalescence by the probability of coalescence at that time for
 1269 these two alleles of J (Rousset, 2004) (page 59), in vector format:

$$1270 \quad \mathbf{T}_n = \sum_{t=1}^n t \mathbf{C}_t$$

1271 (A6-11)

1272 Please note that in Rousset's book or other papers $n=\infty$.

1273 Using the result of equation A6-10 we get:

$$1274 \quad \mathbf{T}_n = \sum_{t=1}^n t \sum_i \lambda_i^{(t-1)} x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1275 (A6-12)

1276 \Leftrightarrow

$$1277 \quad \mathbf{T}_n = \sum_{t=1}^n t \lambda_1^{(t-1)} x_1 \mathbf{e}_1 + \sum_{t=1}^n t \lambda_2^{(t-1)} x_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + \sum_{t=1}^n t \lambda_3^{(t-1)} x_3 \mathbf{e}_3 + \dots + \sum_{t=1}^n t \lambda_i^{(t-1)} x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1278 for the general case of any squared transition matrices (for the present case this sum
 1279 stops at λ_2).

1280 The eigenpairs and scalars are constant through time and we can for now focus on
 1281 the different sums, S_i of each eigenpair of order i :

1282

1283
$$S_i = \sum_{t=1}^n t\lambda_i^{(t-1)} = 1\lambda_i^0 + 2\lambda_i^1 + 3\lambda_i^2 + \dots + n\lambda_i^{(n-1)}$$

1284 \Leftrightarrow

1285
$$\lambda_i S_i = \lambda_i^1 + 2\lambda_i^2 + \dots + (t-1)\lambda_i^{t-1} + n\lambda_i^n$$

1286 We can then set:

1287
$$S_i - \lambda_i S_i = 1 + \lambda_i^1 + \lambda_i^2 + \dots + \lambda_i^{(n-1)} - n\lambda_i^n$$

1288 \Leftrightarrow

1289
$$S_i(1 - \lambda_i) = 1 + \lambda_i^1 + \lambda_i^2 + \dots + \lambda_i^{(n-1)} - n\lambda_i^n$$

1290 \Leftrightarrow

1291
$$S_i(1 - \lambda_i) = S_i' - n\lambda_i^n$$

1292 \Leftrightarrow

1293
$$S_i = \frac{S_i' - n\lambda_i^n}{1 - \lambda_i}$$

1294 where

1295
$$S_i' = 1 + \lambda_i^1 + \lambda_i^2 + \dots + \lambda_i^{(n-1)}$$

1296 \Leftrightarrow

1297
$$\lambda_i S_i' = \lambda_i^1 + \lambda_i^2 + \dots + \lambda_i^{(n-1)} + \lambda_i^n$$

1298 We can again use the fact that:

1299
$$S_i' - \lambda_i S_i' = 1 - \lambda_i^n$$

1300 \Leftrightarrow

1301
$$S_i'(1 - \lambda_i) = 1 - \lambda_i^n$$

1302 \Leftrightarrow

1303
$$S_i' = \frac{1 - \lambda_i^n}{1 - \lambda_i}$$

1304 We can now replace this S_i' in S_i to obtain:

1305
$$S_i = \frac{\frac{1 - \lambda_i^n}{1 - \lambda_i} - n\lambda_i^n}{1 - \lambda_i}$$

1306 \Leftrightarrow

1307
$$S_i = \sum_{t=1}^n t \lambda_i^{(t-1)} = \frac{1 - \lambda_i^n}{(1 - \lambda_i)^2} - n \frac{\lambda_i^n}{1 - \lambda_i} = \frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} - \lambda_i^n \left(\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} + n \right) \right]$$

1308 Now, using this S_i in equation A6-12 yields:

1309
$$\mathbf{T}_n = \sum_i \frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} \left[\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} - \lambda_i^n \left(\frac{1}{1 - \lambda_i} + n \right) \right] x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1310 (A6-13)

1311 Here, simplifying equation A6-13 is possible, but at the expense of another
 1312 approximation. In the case of an isolated dioecious subpopulation, numerical applications
 1313 suggested that if n big (i.e. $n > 400$ generations) or if the subpopulation is big enough ($N > 4$)
 1314 and $n > 10$, then equation A6-13 can be approximated as:

1315
$$\mathbf{T} \approx \sum_i \frac{1}{(1 - \lambda_i)^2} x_i \mathbf{e}_i$$

1316 (A6-14)

1317 For a dioecious population with random mating and even sex-ratio we can write
 1318 Equation A6-2 (see also A6-3) as: $\mathbf{Q}_t = \gamma(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} + \mathbf{v})$.

1319 Eigenpairs of matrix \mathbf{A} are of the form (see A2-4 or Scripts 1,2 and 4):

1320
$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \lambda_1 = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \\ \mathbf{e}_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \lambda_2 = \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \\ \mathbf{e}_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

1321 (A6-15)

1322 Vector \mathbf{v} is composed of a combination of eigenvectors \mathbf{e}_1 and \mathbf{e}_2 :

1323
$$\mathbf{v} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix} = x_1 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \end{pmatrix} + x_2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \end{pmatrix}$$

1324 \Leftrightarrow

$$1325 \quad \begin{cases} 0 = x_1 + x_2 \\ \frac{1}{2N} = x_1 \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} + x_2 \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \end{cases}$$

1326 \Leftrightarrow

$$1327 \quad \begin{cases} x_2 = -x_1 \\ \frac{1}{2N} = x_1 \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2} - 1 + \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \end{cases}$$

1328 \Leftrightarrow

$$1329 \quad \begin{cases} x_2 = -x_1 \\ \frac{1}{2N} = x_1 \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2} = x_1(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2) \end{cases}$$

1330 \Leftrightarrow

$$1331 \quad \begin{cases} x_1 = \frac{1}{2N\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}} = \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \\ x_2 = -\frac{1}{2N\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}} = -\frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \end{cases}$$

1332 (A6-16)

1333 If we combine equations A6-14, and A6-16, we get:

1334

$$1335 \quad \mathbf{T} = \begin{pmatrix} T_I \\ T_S \end{pmatrix} \approx \frac{1}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2} \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_1 \end{pmatrix} - \frac{1}{(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

1336 \Leftrightarrow

$$1337 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{1}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2} - \frac{1}{(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_1}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2} - \frac{\lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1338 \Leftrightarrow

$$1339 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{(1 - \lambda_2)^2 - (1 - \lambda_1)^2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_1(1 - \lambda_2)^2 - \lambda_2(1 - \lambda_1)^2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1340 \Leftrightarrow

$$1341 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{1 + \lambda_2^2 - 2\lambda_2 - 1 - \lambda_1^2 + 2\lambda_1}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_1(1 + \lambda_2^2 - 2\lambda_2) - \lambda_2(1 + \lambda_1^2 - 2\lambda_1)}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1342 \Leftrightarrow

$$1343 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_2^2 - \lambda_1^2 - 2\lambda_2 + 2\lambda_1}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2^2\lambda_1 - 2\lambda_1\lambda_2 - \lambda_2 - \lambda_1^2\lambda_2 + 2\lambda_1\lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1344 \Leftrightarrow

$$1345 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)(\lambda_2 + \lambda_1) + 2(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2 + \lambda_1\lambda_2(\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1346 \Leftrightarrow

$$1347 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{2 - \lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{2N(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)} \left[\frac{1 - \lambda_1\lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1348 \Leftrightarrow

$$1349 \quad \begin{cases} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{2 - \lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{1 - \lambda_1\lambda_2}{(1 - \lambda_1)^2(1 - \lambda_2)^2} \right] \end{cases}$$

1350

(A6-17)

1351 If we use A6-15 in A6-17, we obtain:

1352

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{2 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}}{\left(1 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2} \right] \\
 T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}}{\left(1 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2} \right]
 \end{array} \right.$$

1353 \Leftrightarrow

1354

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{2 - \frac{1 - \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2} + 1 - \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{\left(\frac{1 + \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1 + \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2} \right] \\
 T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)^2 - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}}{\left(\frac{1 + \frac{1}{N} - \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2 \left(\frac{1 + \frac{1}{N} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}}{2}\right)^2} \right]
 \end{array} \right.$$

1355 \Leftrightarrow

1356

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \frac{2 - \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)}{\left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{N}\right)^2 - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}\right)^2} \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{1 - \frac{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2 - 2\frac{1}{N} - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}}{\left(\frac{\left(1 + \frac{1}{N}\right)^2 - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}\right)^2} \right] \end{array} \right.$$

1357 \Leftrightarrow

1358

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \frac{1 + \frac{1}{N}}{\left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2 + 2\frac{1}{N} - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}\right)^2} \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \left[\frac{1 + \frac{1}{2N}}{\left(\frac{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2 + 2\frac{1}{N} - 1 - \left(\frac{1}{N}\right)^2}{4}\right)^2} \right] \end{array} \right.$$

1359 \Leftrightarrow

1360

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} T_I \approx \frac{1}{2N} \frac{1 + \frac{1}{N}}{\left(\frac{1}{2N}\right)^2} \\ T_S \approx \frac{1}{2N} \frac{1 + \frac{1}{2N}}{\left(\frac{1}{2N}\right)^2} \end{array} \right.$$

1361 \Leftrightarrow

1362

$$\begin{cases} T_I \approx 2N \left(1 + \frac{1}{N}\right) \\ T_S \approx 2N \left(1 + \frac{1}{2N}\right) \end{cases}$$

1363 \Leftrightarrow

1364

$$\begin{cases} T_I \approx 2(N + 1) \\ T_S \approx 2N + 1 \end{cases}$$

1365 (A6-18)

1366 This result is the same as in Balloux's paper (Balloux, 2004) (equation 15) with an
1367 even sex ratio:

1368 For a panmictic population of size N_e :

1369

$$\begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \frac{1}{N_e} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I_{t-1}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} \\ Q_{S_t} = \frac{1}{N_e} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I_{t-1}} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} \end{cases}$$

1370 \Leftrightarrow

1371

$$\begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \frac{1}{2N_e} Q_{S_{t-1}} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ Q_{S_t} = \frac{1}{2N_e} Q_{S_{t-1}} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N_e} \end{cases}$$

1372 \Leftrightarrow

1373

$$\begin{cases} Q_{I_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ Q_{S_t} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N_e} \right) Q_{S_{t-1}} + \frac{1}{2N_e} \end{cases}$$

1374 The corresponding transition matrix has the following eigenpair:

1375

$$\begin{cases} \lambda_{e1} = 1 - \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ \lambda_{e2} = 0 \\ \mathbf{e}_{e1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{e}_{e2} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{cases}$$

1376 (A6-19)

1377 Hence:

1378
$$\mathbf{v}_e = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ 1 \\ \frac{1}{2N_e} \end{pmatrix} = x_{e1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} + x_{e2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

1379 \Leftrightarrow

1380
$$\begin{cases} \frac{1}{2N_e} = x_{e1} + x_{e2} \\ \frac{1}{2N_e} = x_{e1} \end{cases}$$

1381 \Leftrightarrow

1382
$$\begin{cases} x_{e1} = \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ x_{e2} = 0 \end{cases}$$

1383 (A6-20)

1384 If we apply equation A6-14 with the values of equations A6-19 and A6-20), we

1385 obtain:

1386
$$\begin{cases} T_{Ie} \approx \frac{1}{\left(1 - 1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}\right)^2} \frac{1}{2N_e} \\ T_{Se} \approx \frac{1}{\left(1 - 1 - \frac{1}{2N_e}\right)^2} \frac{1}{2N_e} \end{cases}$$

1387 \Leftrightarrow

1388
$$\begin{cases} T_{Ie} \approx 2N_e \\ T_{Se} \approx 2N_e \end{cases}$$

1389 (A6-21)

1391 From there, it is easy to understand that the coalescent effective population size can then
1392 be defined as in equation 17 of (Balloux et al., 2003), i.e.:

1393
$$N_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \bar{T}$$

1394 (A6-22)

1395 where \bar{T} is the weighted average of the different T_i 's, here:

$$1396 \quad \bar{T} = \frac{1}{N}T_1 + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)T_S$$

1397 (A6-23)

1398 The weights in fact correspond to the probabilities to sample two genes from the
1399 considered hierarchy: within one individual, from two different individuals within the same
1400 sub-population, from two different sub-populations from the same archipelago, etc...

1401 In our context, for a dioecious and isolated population of size N with an even sex-
1402 ratio, combining equations A6-18, A6-22 and A6-23 leads to:

$$1403 \quad N_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{N} 2(N+1) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right) (2N+1) \right]$$

1404 \Leftrightarrow

$$1405 \quad N_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[2 \left(1 + \frac{1}{N}\right) + 2N + 1 - 2 - \frac{1}{N} \right]$$

1406 \Leftrightarrow

$$1407 \quad N_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[2 + \frac{2}{N} + 2N - 1 - \frac{1}{N} \right]$$

1408 \Leftrightarrow

$$1409 \quad N_e \approx \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{N} + 2N \right]$$

1410 \Leftrightarrow

$$1411 \quad N_e \approx N + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N}$$

1412 (A6-24)

1413 Equation A6-24 is exactly the same as equation 10 in (Balloux, 2004). To give a
1414 biological meaning to this result, it corresponds to the census size (or number of breeders)
1415 plus half an individual that would have been coalescent through random selfing in a WF
1416 population, plus one coalescent individual that would occur in a WF population (which may
1417 sound redundant with the second).

1418

1419 **Appendix 7: Matrix method to compute eigenvalue effective population size in a**
 1420 **dioecious population**

1421 Let $Q_{I(t)}$ and $Q_{S(t)}$ be the probabilities of identity between two alleles at time t within
 1422 individuals and between individuals in a dioecious random mating population. We can then
 1423 use Equations 7 and 8 in the main text:

$$1424 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_f} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_f} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] \\ + \frac{1}{4} \left[\frac{1}{N_m} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N_m} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-1)} \end{cases}$$

1425 \Leftrightarrow

$$1426 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = Q_{I(t-1)} \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{N_f} + \frac{1}{N_m} \right) + Q_{S(t-1)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4N_f} - \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{N_f} + \frac{1}{N_m} \right) \end{cases}$$

1427 (A7-1)

1428 Equation A9-1 has transition matrix (see appendices 1-4):

$$1429 \quad \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4N_f} + \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) & \left(1 - \frac{1}{4N_f} - \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) \end{pmatrix}$$

1430 (A7-2)

1431 To save time we used wxMaxima to find the leading eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} (see Script 1):

$$1432 \quad \lambda_1 = \frac{\sqrt{(16N_f^2 + 1)N_m^2 + 2N_fN_m + N_f^2} + (4N_f - 1)N_m - N_f}{8N_fN_m}$$

1433 \Leftrightarrow

$$1434 \quad \lambda_1 = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{N}{8N_fN_m} + \frac{\sqrt{(4N_fN_m)^2 + N_f^2 + N_m^2 + 2N_fN_m}}{8N_fN_m}$$

1435 \Leftrightarrow

1436

$$\lambda_1 = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{N}{4N_f N_m}\right)^2}$$

1437 which is the same as equation 11 in the main text (QED).

1438

1439 **Appendix 8: Derivatives and Taylor-MacLaurin's expansion series**1440 *Basic notions about derivative functions*

1441 Readers acquainted with derivatives can skip this first section.

1442 The derivative of a function $f(x)$ describes the orientation and speed of variation of
 1443 this function, measured between two points separated by a distance Δx that tends to 0:

1444

$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x + \Delta x) - f(x)}{\Delta x}$$

1445 For the present paper, we will need to compute the derivative of several functions. For
 1446 instance for the function $f(x)=x^n$, then:

1447

$$f'(y) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{(x + \Delta x)^n - x^n}{\Delta x}$$

1448 For any n , beginning with $n=2$ or 3, it is easy to show that:

1449

$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} nx^{(n-1)} + \Delta x \times g(x)$$

1450 where $g(x)$ is a function of x with one term in $x^{m < n}$, one term in Δx^{n-2} and other terms in
 1451 $x\Delta x$, so that the limit when $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ necessary is nx^{n-1} . Then $f'(x)=nx^{n-1}$. It is easy to see that
 1452 the derivative of a sum of functions is simply the sum of derivatives of the different
 1453 functions of this sum.

1454 Next, we need to compute the derivative of $f(g(x))$ or more correctly $(f \circ g)(x)$. For
 1455 this, it will be easier to change of notation:

1456

$$(f \circ g)'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(g(x) + \Delta x) - f(g(x))}{\Delta x}$$

1457

Let $f(g(x) + \Delta x) - f(g(x)) = \Delta u$, and $\Delta v = g(x + \Delta x) - g(x)$, then:

1458

$$(f \circ g)'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta u}{\Delta x}$$

1459 ⇔

1460
$$(f \circ g)'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta u \Delta v}{\Delta v \Delta x}$$

1461 ⇔

1462
$$(f \circ g)'(x) = g'(x) \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta u}{\Delta v}$$

1463 Since it is easy to see that when $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$, then $\Delta v \rightarrow 0$, we can rewrite:

1464
$$(f \circ g)'(x) = f'(u)g'(x)$$

1465 or

1466
$$(f \circ g)'(x) = f'(g(x))g'(x)$$

1467 We then have the necessary tools for Taylor-MacLaurin's expansion series

1468

1469 *Taylor-MacLaurin's expansion series*

1470 In the neighborhood of a , any infinitely differentiable function $f(x)$, writes:

1471
$$f(x) = f(a) + \frac{f'(a)}{1!}(x-a) + \frac{f''(a)}{2!}(x-a)^2 + \dots + \frac{f^{(n)}(a)}{n!}(x-a)^n + \varepsilon$$

1472 Indeed, let f be a derivable function of variable x so that:

1473
$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1(x-a) + a_2(x-a)^2 + a_3(x-a)^3 + a_4(x-a)^4 + \dots$$

1474 If we derivate f , we get:

1475
$$f'(x) = a_1 + 2a_2(x-a) + 3a_3(x-a)^2 + 4a_4(x-a)^3 + \dots$$

1476
$$f''(x) = 2a_2 + 3 \times 2 \times a_3(x-a) + 4 \times 3 \times a_4(x-a)^2 + \dots$$

1477
$$f'''(x) = 3 \times 2 \times a_3 + 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times a_4(x-a) + \dots$$

1478 If $x \rightarrow a$, then $(x-a) \rightarrow 0$ and:

1479 $f'(x) = a_1$

1480 $f''(x) = 2a_2$

1481 $f'''(x) = 3 \times 2 \times a_3$

1482 $f''''(x) = 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times a_3$

1483 $f^{(n)}(x) = n! \times a_n$

1484 where $f^{(n)}$ is the n th derivative of f .

1485 We can thus set that, in the neighborhood of a :

1486
$$a_n = \frac{f^{(n)}(x)}{n!}$$

1487 From there we can rewrite $f(x)$ in the neighborhood of a :

1488
$$f(x) = \frac{f(a)}{0!} + \frac{f'(a)}{1!}(x-a) + \frac{f''(a)}{2!}(x-a)^2 + \frac{f'''(a)}{3!}(x-a)^3 + \dots$$

1489 If $a \rightarrow 0$, $f(x)$ writes (QED):

1490
$$f(x) = f(0) + f'(0)(x) + \frac{f''(0)}{2!}(x)^2 + \frac{f'''(0)}{3!}(x)^3 + \dots$$

1491 This method will offer very good approximations of cumbersome functions of small
 1492 variables (e.g. $1/(2N)$ or $1/N^2$).

1493

1494 *Examples of Taylor-MacLaurin's expansion series*

1495 We need to find a proxy for $\sqrt{1+X}$ and for $1/(1-X)$, when X is small.

1496 For $f(x) = \sqrt{x}$:

1497
$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sqrt{x + \Delta x} - \sqrt{x}}{\Delta x}$$

1498 \Leftrightarrow

1499
$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{[\sqrt{x + \Delta x} - \sqrt{x}][\sqrt{x + \Delta x} + \sqrt{x}]}{\Delta x [\sqrt{x + \Delta x} + \sqrt{x}]}$$

1500 \Leftrightarrow

1501
$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{x + \Delta x + \sqrt{x + \Delta x} \sqrt{x} - \sqrt{x} \sqrt{x + \Delta x} - x}{\Delta x [\sqrt{x + \Delta x} + \sqrt{x}]}$$

1502 \Leftrightarrow

1503
$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta x [\sqrt{x + \Delta x} + \sqrt{x}]}$$

1504 \Leftrightarrow

1505
$$f'(x) = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{\sqrt{x + \Delta x} + \sqrt{x}}$$

1506 \Leftrightarrow

1507
$$f'(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}}$$

1508 Let $g(X)$ be:

1509
$$g(X) = \sqrt{1 + X}$$

1510 Then:

1511
$$g'(X) = (\sqrt{1 + X})' \times 1$$

1512 \Leftrightarrow

1513
$$g'(X) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{1 + X}}$$

1514 For the function $1/x$:

1515
$$\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)' = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\left(\frac{1}{x + \Delta x}\right) - \frac{1}{x}}{\Delta x}$$

1516 \Leftrightarrow

1517
$$\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)' = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\frac{x - x - \Delta x}{x(x + \Delta x)}}{\Delta x}$$

1518 \Leftrightarrow

1519
$$\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)' = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{-\Delta x}{x(x + \Delta x)\Delta x}$$

1520 \Leftrightarrow

1521
$$\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)' = \lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0} \frac{-1}{x(x + \Delta x)}$$

1522 ⇔

1523
$$\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)' = \frac{-1}{x^2}$$

1524 Using the same approach as for $g'(X)$:

1525
$$g''(X) = -\frac{1}{2^2(\sqrt{1+X})^3}$$

1526 If we now use Taylor for $g(X) = \sqrt{1+X}$ in the neighborhood of a :

1527
$$g(X) \approx \frac{g(a)}{0!}(X-a)^0 + \frac{g'(a)}{1!}(X-a)^1 + \frac{g''(a)}{2!}(X-a)^2 + \dots$$

1528 ⇔

1529
$$g(X) \approx \frac{\sqrt{1+a}}{0!}(X-a)^0 + \frac{\frac{1}{2\sqrt{1+a}}}{1!}(X-a)^1 + \frac{-\frac{1}{2^2(\sqrt{1+a})^3}}{2!}(X-a)^2 + \dots$$

1530 When $a \rightarrow 0$, we get:

1531
$$g(X) = \sqrt{1+X} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}X - \frac{1}{8}X^2 + \dots$$

1532 The same result can be obtained with the command "taylor(sqrt(1+X),X,0,3)" in wxMaxima

1533 (Vodopivec, 2017).

1534
$$g(X) = \sqrt{1+X} = 1 + \frac{1}{2}X - \frac{1}{8}X^2 + \frac{1}{16}X^3 \dots$$

1535 Now, if $X \ll 1$, we can approximate this expression as:

1536
$$\sqrt{1+X} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2}X - \frac{1}{8}X^2$$

1537 The first and second derivatives of $1/(1-X)$ are $1/(1-X)^2$ and $2(1-X)/(1-X)^4$. We can use

1538 Taylor-MacLaurin again and write: $1/(1-X) = 1+X+X^2+X^3+\dots$ (note that the same result would

1539 have been obtained with Maxima (Vodopivec, 2017) typing "taylor(1/(1-X),X,0,3)").

1540

1541 **Appendix 9: Finding the root of $N_{e_Eq3} - N_{e_Eq13}$**

1542 Since Equation 15 gave an almost perfect estimate of equation 13, we studied the
 1543 sign of $\Delta N_e = N_{e_Eq3} - N_{e_Eq15}$ instead of $N_{e_Eq3} - N_{e_Eq13}$ for the sake of simplicity.

1544
$$\Delta N_e = \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N} - \frac{4N_f N_m}{N} - \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4} \frac{N}{4N_f N_m}$$

1545 \Leftrightarrow

1546
$$\Delta N_e = \frac{1}{2N} - \frac{1}{4} \frac{N}{4N_f N_m}$$

1547 \Rightarrow

1548
$$\Delta N_e \propto \frac{1}{N} - \frac{N}{8N_f N_m} <$$

1549 \Rightarrow

1550
$$\Delta N_e \propto \frac{8N_f N_m - N^2}{8N_f N_m N}$$

1551 \Rightarrow

1552
$$\Delta N_e \propto 8N_f N_m - (N_f + N_m)^2$$

1553 \Rightarrow

1554
$$\Delta N_e \propto 8N_f N_m - N_f^2 - N_m^2 - 2N_f N_m$$

1555 \Rightarrow

1556
$$\Delta N_e \propto 6N_f N_m - N_f^2 - N_m^2$$

1557 We can divide the right term by N_f^2 , then, noting $SR = N_m/N_f$:

1558
$$\Delta N_e \propto 6SR - 1 - SR^2$$

1559 \Rightarrow

1560
$$\Delta N_e \propto SR^2 - 6SR + 1$$

1561 \Rightarrow

1562
$$\Delta N_e \propto SR^2 - 2 \times 3SR + 9 - 8$$

1563 \Rightarrow

1564
$$\Delta N_e \propto (SR - 3)^2 - 8$$

1565 We need to find the two roots of the right term, which must satisfy:

1566
$$(SR - 3)^2 = 8$$

1567 \Leftrightarrow

1568
$$SR - 3 = \pm\sqrt{8}$$

1569 \Leftrightarrow

1570
$$SR = 3 \pm \sqrt{8}$$

1571 \Leftrightarrow

1572
$$\begin{cases} SR_1 = 3 + \sqrt{8} \approx 5.8284 \\ SR_2 = 3 - \sqrt{8} \approx 0.1716 \end{cases}$$

1573 A sex-ratio above 1 is not relevant here, since an excess of females would lead to
 1574 the same result as in populations with an even sex-ratio. Consequently, SR_2 is the only
 1575 relevant root. From there, it can be seen that Balloux's equation will provide an over-
 1576 estimate when $SR > SR_2$, an under-estimate when $SR < SR_2$ and will be exact when
 1577 $SR = SR_2 = 3 - 2\sqrt{2}$.

1578
 1579 **Appendix 10: Balloux's like method to compute F_{IS} based N_e**

1580 Let Q_I and Q_S be the probabilities to sample twice the same allele in one individual
 1581 and between individuals from the same population, respectively, u the mutation rate, then,
 1582 for a dioecious population with an even sex-ratio and random mating, we can set the
 1583 following recurrences between generation t and $t-1$ (see equations 7 and 8 with $N_f = N_m$):

1584
$$\begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = (1 - u)^2 Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = (1 - u)^2 \left[\frac{1}{N} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \right] \end{cases}$$

1585 \Leftrightarrow

1586
$$\begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = (1 - u)^2 Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = (1 - u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} Q_{I(t-1)} + (1 - u)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} + (1 - u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

1587 (A9-1)

1588 Let \mathbf{Q}_t and \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} be the vectors defining genetic identities at generations t and $t-1$, \mathbf{A} the
 1589 transition matrix and \mathbf{v} the vector of residuals, then:

$$1590 \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{Q}_t = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{I(t)} \\ Q_{S(t)} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1-u)^2 \\ (1-u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} & (1-u)^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right) \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{v} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ (1-u)^2 \frac{1}{2N} \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

1591 (A9-2)

1592 and $\mathbf{Q}_t = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} + \mathbf{V}$.

1593 At equilibrium, we can write that the vector of genetic identities \mathbf{Q} writes $\mathbf{Q} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{V}$,

1594 where $\mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is the identity matrix (see appendix 5).

1595 To solve this equation, and get Q_I and Q_S at equilibrium, we used wxMaxima
 1596 17.10.1 (Vodopivec, 2017) as detailed in the section wxMaxima scripts, Script 2. Taking
 1597 into account that $u \ll 1$, we obtained:

$$1598 \quad F_{IS} = \frac{Q_I - Q_S}{1 - Q_S} \approx -\frac{1}{2N + 1}$$

1599 (A9-3)

1600 The same results can be obtained with classic algebra, without the use of matrix
 1601 computations, but it is much faster this way. This is also the same results as equation 8 in
 1602 Balloux's paper. It is worth mentioning here that equation A10-3 can also theoretically give
 1603 access to the census size of individuals in the population (N) or, more precisely, to the
 1604 exact number of adult parents of the individuals in the population, that some may call the
 1605 effective number of breeders:

$$1606 \quad N = -\frac{1 + F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}}$$

1607 (A9-4)

1608 If we go back to equation 16 of the main manuscript, we can compute the
 1609 eigenvalue effective population size as:

$$1610 \quad N_e \approx N + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4N}$$

1611 (A9-5)

1612 If we combine equations A9-5 with A9-4, we obtain:

$$1613 \quad N_e \approx -\frac{1 + F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}} + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{4 \frac{1 + F_{IS}}{2F_{IS}}}$$

1614 \Leftrightarrow

$$1615 \quad N_e \approx -\frac{1}{2F_{IS}} - \frac{F_{IS}}{2(1 + F_{IS})}$$

1616 (A9-6)

1617 Now, with a stronger approximation, $N_e \approx N + 1/2$, which, combined with equation A9-4
 1618 yields Pudovkin et al.'s equation 3 (see equation 4 of the present manuscript). We can also
 1619 notice that A9-6 is the average of equations 4 (Pudovkin et al. second equation) and 6
 1620 (Balloux).

1621

1622 **Appendix 11: Equilibrium value for F_{IS} in a dioecious population (general case)**

1623 For this we need to use equation A6-1 and add a mutation rate u so that equation
 1624 A6-1 becomes:

$$1625 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)}(1 - u)^2 \\ Q_{S(t)} = Q_{I(t-1)} \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{N_f} + \frac{1}{N_m} \right) (1 - u)^2 + Q_{S(t-1)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{4N_f} - \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) (1 - u)^2 \\ \quad \quad \quad + \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{N_f} + \frac{1}{N_m} \right) (1 - u)^2 \end{cases}$$

1626 (A10-1)

1627 The transition matrix and the associated vectors of this equation are:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbf{Q}_t = \begin{pmatrix} Q_{I(t)} \\ Q_{S(t)} \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1-u)^2 \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4N_f} + \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) (1-u)^2 & \left(1 - \frac{1}{4N_f} - \frac{1}{4N_m} \right) (1-u)^2 \end{pmatrix} \\ \mathbf{V} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{1}{N_f} + \frac{1}{N_m} \right) (1-u)^2 \end{pmatrix} \end{array} \right.$$

1629 and equation A7-1 can be rewritten as $\mathbf{Q}_t = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{Q}_{t-1} + \mathbf{V}$.

1630 At equilibrium, the vector of genetic identities satisfies the equation $\mathbf{Q} = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{A})^{-1} \cdot \mathbf{V}$,
 1631 where $\mathbf{I} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ is the identity matrix (see appendix 5).

1632 To solve this equation, and get Q_I and Q_S at equilibrium, we used wxMaxima
 1633 17.10.1 (Vodopivec, 2017), as detailed in the section wxMaxima scripts (Script 3) and
 1634 obtained:

$$1635 F_{IS} = \frac{(N_m + N_f)u^2 - 2(N_m + N_f)u + N_m + N_f}{(N_m + N_f)u^2 - 2(N_m + N_f)u + N_m + N_f + 8N_m N_f}$$

1636 \Leftrightarrow

$$1637 F_{IS} = - \frac{(N_m + N_f)(1-u)^2}{(N_m + N_f)(1-u)^2 + 8N_m N_f}$$

1638 (A10-2)

1639 Terms in u are small in front of 1 so that equation A7-2 can be simplified as:

$$1640 F_{IS} \approx - \frac{N_m + N_f}{N_m + N_f + 8N_m N_f}$$

1641 (A10-3)

1642

1643 **Appendix 12: Effective population size of an isolated monogamous population**

1644 We will use the same notations as in other sections. Monogamy implies an even
 1645 sex ratio in the pool of adults that are involved in a mating. For the identity within
 1646 individuals, the recurrence stays the same as in polygamous populations. The recursion

1647 for the identity between individuals can be determined by conditioning on the ancestry of
 1648 the sampled pair in the previous generation. One possibility is that the two sampled
 1649 individuals are sibs, i.e., they share the same parents, which is true with probability
 1650 $1/(N/2)$. In this case, with probability $1/2$, the two alleles will have come from the same
 1651 parent, in which case they are equally likely to be derived from a single parental allele or
 1652 from both parental alleles. In the former case, the sampled alleles are necessarily IBD,
 1653 whereas in the latter case, the probability that they are IBD is $Q_{I(t-1)}$. Alternatively, with
 1654 probability $1/2$, each sampled allele may have come from a different parent, in which case
 1655 the probability that they are IBD is $Q_{S(t-1)}$. The second possibility, which has probability $1 -$
 1656 $1/(N/2)$, is that the two sampled individuals are not sibs, in which case the probability that
 1657 the sampled alleles are IBD is $Q_{S(t-1)}$. We can thus set the following recurrence:

$$1658 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}N} \left[\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} Q_{I(t-1)} \right) + \frac{1}{2} Q_{S(t-1)} \right] + \left(1 - \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}N} \right) Q_{S(t-1)} \end{cases}$$

1659 \Leftrightarrow

$$1660 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = Q_{I(t-1)} \frac{1}{2N} + Q_{S(t-1)} \left(\frac{1}{N} + 1 - \frac{1}{\frac{1}{2}N} \right) + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

1661 \Leftrightarrow

$$1662 \quad \begin{cases} Q_{I(t)} = Q_{S(t-1)} \\ Q_{S(t)} = Q_{I(t-1)} \frac{1}{2N} + Q_{S(t-1)} \left(1 - \frac{1}{N} \right) + \frac{1}{2N} \end{cases}$$

1663 Using Maxima, it is easy to compute the leading eigenvalue of the corresponding transition
 1664 matrix as:

$$1665 \quad \lambda_1 = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2N} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{N} \right)^2}$$

1666 For X small, Taylor-MacLaurin of $\sqrt{1 + X} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2}X$, hence:

1667
$$\lambda_1 \approx \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2N} + \frac{1}{2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{N} \right)^2 \right]$$

1668 ⇔

1669
$$\lambda_1 \approx 1 - \frac{1}{2N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right)$$

1670 The eigenvalue effective population size is:

1671
$$N_e \approx \frac{1}{2(1 - \lambda_1)}$$

1672 ⇔

1673
$$N_e \approx \frac{1}{2 \left(1 - 1 + \frac{1}{2N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right) \right)}$$

1674 ⇔

1675
$$N_e \approx \frac{1}{\frac{1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{2N} \right)}$$

1676 ⇔

1677
$$N_e \approx \frac{N}{1 - \frac{1}{2N}}$$

1678 ⇔

1679 Using Taylor-MacLaurin again leads to:

1680
$$\frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2N}} \approx 1 + \frac{1}{2N} + \left(\frac{1}{2N} \right)^2$$

1681 Then:

1682
$$N_e \approx N \left[1 + \frac{1}{2N} + \left(\frac{1}{2N} \right)^2 \right]$$

1683 ⇔

1684
$$N_e \approx N + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2N}$$

1685 This result is exactly the same as for a dioecious pangamic population with even
1686 sex ratio.
1687

1688

wxMaxima scripts

1689

1690 Script 1: Computing the eigenvalues of Matrix A (equation A6-2)

1691 (%i1) `A: matrix([0,1], [(1/N_f+1/N_m)/8,1-1/(4·N_f)-1/(4·N_m)]);`

1692 (A)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \frac{\frac{1}{N_m} + \frac{1}{N_f}}{8} & -\frac{1}{4N_m} - \frac{1}{4N_f} + 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

1693 (%i2) `eigenvalues(A);`

1694 (%o2)
$$\left[\left[-\frac{\sqrt{(16N_f^2+1)N_m^2+2N_fN_m+N_f^2+(1-4N_f)N_m+N_f}}{8N_fN_m}, \frac{\sqrt{(16N_f^2+1)N_m^2+2N_fN_m+N_f^2+(4N_f-1)N_m-N_f}}{8N_fN_m} \right], [1,1] \right]$$

1695

1696 Script 2: recomputing N_e and F_{is} in dioecious populations with an even sex ratio

1697 (%i1) `A: matrix(`
1698 `[0,(1-u)^2],`
1699 `[(1-u)^2/(2·N),(1-u)^2·(1-1/N)]`
1700 `);`

1701 (A)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1-u)^2 \\ \frac{(1-u)^2}{2N} & \left(1 - \frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

1702 (%i2) `I: matrix(`
1703 `[1,0],`
1704 `[0,1]`
1705 `);`

1706 (I)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

1707 (%i3) `V: matrix(`
1708 `[0],`
1709 `[(1-u)^2/(2·N)]`
1710 `);`

1711 (V) $\left(\frac{0}{\frac{(1-u)^2}{2N}}\right)$

1712 (%i4) `Q:invert(I-A).V;`

1713 (Q) $\left(\frac{\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}}{\frac{(1-u)^2}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}}\right)$

1714 (%i5) `QI:(1-u)^4/(2·N·(-(1-u)^4/(2·N)-(1-1/N)·(1-u)^2+1));`

1715 (QI) $\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}$

1716 (%i6) `QS:(1-u)^2/(2·N·(-(1-u)^4/(2·N)-(1-1/N)·(1-u)^2+1));`

1717 (QS) $\frac{(1-u)^2}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}$

1718 (%i7) `FIS:(QI-QS)/(1-QS);`

1719 (FIS) $\frac{\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)} - \frac{(1-u)^2}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}}{1 - \frac{(1-u)^2}{2N\left(-\frac{(1-u)^4}{2N}-\left(1-\frac{1}{N}\right)(1-u)^2+1\right)}}$

1720 (%i9) `FIS2:ratsimp(FIS);`

1721 (FIS2) $-\frac{u^2-2u+1}{u^2-2u+2N+1}$

1722 (%i10) `eigenvalues(A);`

1723 (%o10)

1724 $\left[\left[-\frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}(u^2-2u+1)+(1-N)u^2+(2N-2)u-N+1}{2N}, \frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}(u^2-2u+1)+(N-1)u^2+(2-2N)u+N-1}{2N}\right], [1,1]\right]$

1725 (%i11) `λ1:ratsubst(0,u,(sqrt(N^2+1)·(u^2-2·u+1)+(N-1)·u^2+(2-2·N)·u+N-1)/(2·N));`

1726 (λ1) $\frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}+N-1}{2N}$

1727

1728 **Script 3: Computing F_{IS} in a dioecious population (general case)**

1729 (%i2) `A: matrix(`

1730 $[0,(1-u)^2],$
 1731 $[(1-u)^2 \cdot (1/(4 \cdot N_f) + 1/(4 \cdot N_m)) / 2, (1 - 1/(4 \cdot N_f) - 1/(4 \cdot N_m)) \cdot (1-u)^2]$
 1732);

1733 (A)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & (1-u)^2 \\ \frac{\left(\frac{1}{4N_m} + \frac{1}{4N_f}\right)(1-u)^2}{2} & \left(-\frac{1}{4N_m} - \frac{1}{4N_f} + 1\right)(1-u)^2 \end{pmatrix}$$

1734 (%i3) **V: matrix(**

1735 $[0],$

1736 $[(1-u)^2 \cdot (1/N_f + 1/N_m) / 8]$

1737);

1738 (V)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\left(\frac{1}{N_m} + \frac{1}{N_f}\right)(1-u)^2}{8} \end{pmatrix}$$

1739 (%i4) **I: matrix(**

1740 $[1,0],$

1741 $[0,1]$

1742);

1743 (I)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

1744 (%i5) **Q:invert(I-A).V;**

1745 (Q)
$$\begin{pmatrix} \frac{\left(\frac{1}{N_m} + \frac{1}{N_f}\right)(1-u)^4}{8 \left(\frac{\left(\frac{1}{4N_m} + \frac{1}{4N_f}\right)(1-u)^4}{2} - \left(-\frac{1}{4N_m} - \frac{1}{4N_f} + 1\right)(1-u)^2 + 1 \right)} \\ \frac{\left(\frac{1}{N_m} + \frac{1}{N_f}\right)(1-u)^2}{8 \left(\frac{\left(\frac{1}{4N_m} + \frac{1}{4N_f}\right)(1-u)^4}{2} - \left(-\frac{1}{4N_m} - \frac{1}{4N_f} + 1\right)(1-u)^2 + 1 \right)} \end{pmatrix}$$

1746 (%i6) **ratsimp(%);**

1747 (%o6)
$$\begin{pmatrix} -\frac{(N_m + N_f)u^4 + (-4N_m - 4N_f)u^3 + (6N_m + 6N_f)u^2 + (-4N_m - 4N_f)u + N_m + N_f}{(N_m + N_f)u^4 + (-4N_m - 4N_f)u^3 + ((8N_f + 4)N_m + 4N_f)u^2 - 16N_fN_mu - N_m - N_f} \\ -\frac{(N_m + N_f)u^2 + (-2N_m - 2N_f)u + N_m + N_f}{(N_m + N_f)u^4 + (-4N_m - 4N_f)u^3 + ((8N_f + 4)N_m + 4N_f)u^2 - 16N_fN_mu - N_m - N_f} \end{pmatrix}$$

1748 (%i7)

1749 $QI:-((N_m+N_f)\cdot u^4+(-4\cdot N_m-4\cdot N_f)\cdot u^3+(6\cdot N_m+6\cdot N_f)\cdot u^2+(-4\cdot N_m-4\cdot N_f)\cdot u$
 1750 $+N_m+N_f)/((N_m+N_f)\cdot u^4+(-4\cdot N_m-4\cdot N_f)\cdot u^3+((8\cdot N_f+4)\cdot N_m+4\cdot N_f)\cdot u^2-1$
 1751 $6\cdot N_f\cdot N_m\cdot u-N_m-N_f);$

1752 (QI)
$$\frac{-(N_m+N_f)u^4-(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3-(6N_m+6N_f)u^2-(-4N_m-4N_f)u-N_m-N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^4+(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3+((8N_f+4)N_m+4N_f)u^2-16N_fN_mu-N_m-N_f}$$

1753 (%i8)

1754 $QS:-((N_m+N_f)\cdot u^2+(-2\cdot N_m-2\cdot N_f)\cdot u+N_m+N_f)/((N_m+N_f)\cdot u^4+(-4\cdot N_m-4\cdot$
 1755 $N_f)\cdot u^3+((8\cdot N_f+4)\cdot N_m+4\cdot N_f)\cdot u^2-16\cdot N_f\cdot N_m\cdot u-N_m-N_f);$

1756 (QS)
$$\frac{-(N_m+N_f)u^2-(-2N_m-2N_f)u-N_m-N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^4+(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3+((8N_f+4)N_m+4N_f)u^2-16N_fN_mu-N_m-N_f}$$

1757 (%i9) $FIS:(QI-QS)/(1-QS);$

1758 (FIS)

1759

1760
$$\frac{\frac{-(N_m+N_f)u^4-(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3-(6N_m+6N_f)u^2-(-4N_m-4N_f)u-N_m-N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^4+(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3+((8N_f+4)N_m+4N_f)u^2-16N_fN_mu-N_m-N_f} - \frac{-(N_m+N_f)u^2-(-2N_m-2N_f)u-N_m-N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^4+(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3+((8N_f+4)N_m+4N_f)u^2-16N_fN_mu-N_m-N_f}}{1 - \frac{-(N_m+N_f)u^2-(-2N_m-2N_f)u-N_m-N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^4+(-4N_m-4N_f)u^3+((8N_f+4)N_m+4N_f)u^2-16N_fN_mu-N_m-N_f}}$$

1761 (%i10) $FIS2:ratsimp(FIS);$

1762 (FIS2)
$$-\frac{(N_m+N_f)u^2+(-2N_m-2N_f)u+N_m+N_f}{(N_m+N_f)u^2+(-2N_m-2N_f)u+(8N_f+1)N_m+N_f}$$

1763

1764 **Script 4: Computing eigenpairs in a dioecious population (even sex-ratio)**

1765 (%i1) $A: matrix($

1766 $[0,1],$

1767 $[1/(2\cdot N),1-1/N]$

1768 $);$

1769 (A)
$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ \frac{1}{2N} & 1 - \frac{1}{N} \end{pmatrix}$$

1770 (%i2) $eigenvectors(A);$

1771 (%o2) $\left[\left[\left[-\frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}-N+1}{2N}, \frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}+N-1}{2N} \right], [1,1] \right], \left[\left[1, -\frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}-N+1}{2N} \right], \left[1, \frac{\sqrt{N^2+1}+N-1}{2N} \right] \right] \right]$

1772

1773 **Script 5: Computing partial Q in a dioecious population (even sex-ratio)**

1774 (%i7) **D:** matrix(

1775 $[\lambda_1^{t-1}, 0],$

1776 $[0, \lambda_2^{t-1}]$

1777);

1778 (D) $\begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1^{t-1} & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_2^{t-1} \end{pmatrix}$

1779 (%i8) **P:** matrix(

1780 $[1,1],$

1781 $[\lambda_1, \lambda_2]$

1782);

1783 (P) $\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ \lambda_1 & \lambda_2 \end{pmatrix}$

1784 --> ;

1785 --> **Q_1:** matrix(

1786 $[Q_I_1],$

1787 $[Q_S_1]$

1788);

1789 (Q_1) $\begin{pmatrix} Q_I_1 \\ Q_S_1 \end{pmatrix}$

1790 (%i10) **Q_partial:** $\gamma^{t-1} \cdot P \cdot D \cdot \text{invert}(P) \cdot Q_1;$

1791 (Q_partial) $\begin{pmatrix} \gamma^{t-1} \left(\lambda_1^{t-1} \left(\frac{Q_I_1 \lambda_2}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} - \frac{Q_S_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} \right) + \lambda_2^{t-1} \left(\frac{Q_S_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} - \frac{Q_I_1 \lambda_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} \right) \right) \\ \gamma^{t-1} \left(\lambda_1^t \left(\frac{Q_I_1 \lambda_2}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} - \frac{Q_S_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} \right) + \lambda_2^t \left(\frac{Q_S_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} - \frac{Q_I_1 \lambda_1}{\lambda_2 - \lambda_1} \right) \right) \end{pmatrix}$

1792